

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D8.1

Conceptual design of the SSbD toolbox

WP 8 — T8.1

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Abstract

Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) is a strategy to develop new chemical substances, materials and products keeping in mind both the functionality and the potential impact on human beings and the environment. It is one of the core strategies of the European Commission (EC) ambition to achieve a toxic-free environment by 2050.

To support this strategy, the PARC project aims to develop a toolbox, which will be a collection of variable tools functionally interconnected, methods and instruments to support designers, developers, risk assessors from industry, academia and governments in addressing questions about chemical safety, sustainability and socio-economic impact. The key goals of the toolbox are to provide: a) structured inventory and overview of tools, methods and approaches for SSbD assessment through the innovation process, b) a structured workflow interlinking the various tools with input-output relationships, methods and approaches through the innovation process, and c) a decision-support approach to support interpretation and follow-up actions.

The tools and methods will be structured and mapped following the stage of development of the chemical or material into commercial products (e.g. innovation stage in the stage-gate model, or the Technology Readiness Level), as well as regarding the steps of the EC SSbD framework that they can support. In a first step the tools will be mapped to two stages: early-stage development and later-stage development.

This deliverable describes the approach used to develop the PARC SSbD Toolbox. Available tools and methods in the safety and sustainability dimensions are reviewed. The key questions for safety, sustainability and functionality aspects, and emerging findings from stakeholder elicitation are presented. The blueprint for the toolbox and current proposal for computational implementation are presented as well.

Key Words

Safety, sustainability, green chemistry, Green Deal, innovation stages, QSARs, exposure models, LCA, SSbD toolbox

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1. Introduction

1.1 Safe and sustainable by design as core principle

The chemical industry is essential to the functioning of society providing the materials and products that are used in a wide range of applications ranging from agriculture and healthcare to energy and transportation. However, the production and use of chemicals also has a significant impact on the environment and human health. To address these concerns and ensure the sustainable transition of the chemical industry, the concept of "Safe and Sustainable by Design" (SSbD) has been introduced. SSbD is a prevention-focused strategy that requires a transition of the current end-of-pipe approaches towards inclusive early-stage innovation-based thinking. SSbD thinking requires systemic changes and action and cooperation within the ecosystem of industry, risk- and sustainability assessors and specialists, academia and policy makers.

Essentially, SSbD is a prevention strategy that addresses safety and sustainability as early on in the design phase as possible. It addresses the so-called Collingridge Dilemma which has been formulated thus: *"When change is easy, the need for it cannot be foreseen; when the need for change is apparent, change has become expensive, difficult, and time-consuming. Decisions taken early in the process have far reaching influences on the future and success of a technology"* (Collingridge, 1980). SSbD thus aims to steer innovation towards an outcome with improved safety and sustainability characteristics. As a concept, SSbD is general and applicable to all new (technological) developments but is addressed here specifically from the context chemicals, materials and products.

SSbD is a holistic approach that integrates safety, human health, environmental, economic and social considerations along with functionality requirements into the design and development of chemicals and chemical products. Thus, SSbD is a comprehensive approach that represents a paradigm shift that can only be achieved by combining the joint efforts of industry, academia, experts and policy makers.

1.2 EU policy context — positioning SSbD

With the Green Deal, the EU set out to transition to a climate neutral and toxic free society, whilst maintaining and enhancing a strong and competitive EU market. To this end, the Commission developed a comprehensive set of action plans addressing specific economic sectors such energy, agriculture, transport and chemicals. The Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is the essential EU action plan for achieving a toxic-free and safe environment. The strategy comprises large number of policy actions, emphasizing the need for prevention approaches. As explained above, SSbD is the ultimate prevention strategy that steers innovation towards chemicals, materials and products towards improved safety and sustainability characteristics.

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Figure 1. The toxic-free hierarchy - a new hierarchy in chemicals management

JRC developed a framework for Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (Caldeira et al., 2022b) chemicals and materials which focusses on two elemental aspects: addressing the (re)design of a chemical or a material and developing an assessment procedure that gives an outline of how an SSbD assessment could be performed. In a recent workshop a number of case studies have been presented that took an in-depth look at the machinery of the framework: is it possible to follow all the steps within the framework and what is needed to do so.

The EU SSbD framework as developed by JRC serves as an important milestone and forms a secure fundament and starting point for the development of the PARC SSbD Toolbox.

To support the process of further development of the SSbD framework the Commission published a Recommendation which invites and stimulates stakeholders (member states, academia, and industry) to test and gain hands-on experience with the framework to add to the further development.

Additionally, the Commission published the Strategic Research and Innovation plan which addresses the scientific knowledge that needs to be developed in the coming period to enable the goals of the green deal and the Zero Pollution Ambition to be achieved. The SSbD framework is one of the fundamental cornerstones of these strategies and consequently an important element addressed in the SRIP.

On top of this, SSbD takes up an important role in the Transition Pathways document of the chemical industry, which describes the path to be taken by the chemical industry in relation to multiple transition challenges (e.g. energy, climate, zero-pollution).

All in all, SSbD is one of the fundamental strategies positioned by the EC to help achieve the ambitious goals of the Green Deal.

In this context, the PARC partnership serves as an important vehicle for the development of knowledge for the next generation risk assessment of chemicals, of which SSbd is an inseparable element. From an SSbD perspective, PARC operates at the science-policy interface and focuses on being the primary focal point for gathering knowledge and information to enable the operationalisation of SSbD, including the development of a toolbox and a supporting structure.

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1.3 SSbD — essential elements for operationalization

SSbD thinking is crucial and instrumental in steering innovation towards safer, more sustainable and more social-economically responsible chemicals, materials and products. SSbD-thinking helps us to navigate towards innovations that are safer and ‘greener’, and as such guides innovation. The main question of course is: how can we develop this to an operational strategy?

First of all it is important to set the stage and define some boundaries. Within the context of PARC we are specifically looking and aiming at substances including chemicals and materials. Secondly, SSbD is a transition that is set within a policy context which provides us with two important pieces of guidance: focus on the substitution of substances with unwanted properties and focus on guiding the design of a chemical substance with optimal properties (safe, sustainable, functional, socio-economical).

- SSbD as an approach for the (re)design of existing chemical products with the aim of optimizing and balancing the overall product performance (safe, sustainable, functional, socio-economical).
- SSbD as a guiding approach in developing new chemicals and materials with optimal properties (safe, sustainable, functional, socio-economical).

Elemental for the first bullet is a method that allows for the assessment of a chemical, material or product and a set of criteria to somehow identify the ‘level’ of SSbD. The recently developed SSbD framework by the EC provides us with a general outline of an assessment procedure and a set of ideas to come to an SSbD score.

Guiding the development of new chemicals and materials requires linking safety, sustainability and functionality with the process of innovation. In the stage gate model, the product in development is evaluated as per the SSbD framework and allowed to go to the next stage if it passes the evaluation. Such an approach ensures that the chemical/product in development always remains SSbD. There is however the larger question of the type of data and assessment possible at each stage, particularly early stages where very little data is available. ISO 14006 provides some guidance on linking environmental aspects to product design (Figure 2).

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Figure 2. Integration of environmental aspects in product design (Source: ISO 14006 Environmental management systems - Guidelines for incorporating ecodesign)

From qualitative information in the early stages, laboratory or prototype information becomes available, to quantitative information on actual products at commercial scale. Another gap is how the SSbD assessment effectively contributes to the formulation of (re)design actions.

Use cases of scenarios where the SSbD Toolbox will be used need to be developed and tested to further enhance the value, user friendliness and features of the SSbD toolbox. A use case could in principle describe a particular assessment question in the context of an innovation stage, and some knowledge of the lifecycle of chemical/product.

Connecting the whole of PARC

These types of measures will be developed in the framework of the PARC project and will be integrated as backend tools to the toolbox that will be developed. For example, from WP4, HBM data and a holistic methodology to analyse them will be produced, from WP5, hazard assessment tools and bioinformatics algorithms will be introduced, in WP6, risk assessment tools and pharmacokinetic models and in WP7 the FAIRness of the data with innovative analysis techniques i.e., combination techniques for heterogeneous data.

The main scope of the PARC SSbD toolbox is to aid the operationalization of the SSbD framework. The goal is to set-up a structure that on the one hand allows for the development of a toolbox that supports making the EC SSbD framework operational, and on the other hand takes into account the specific input of users and stakeholders and supplies them with the relevant support to enable them to make SSbD operational. Through the PARC SSbD toolbox, safety and sustainability assessment tools as well as newly developed PARC tools will be integrated.

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The key goals of the toolbox are to provide: a) a structured inventory and overview of tools, methods, and approaches for SSbD assessment through the innovation process, b) a structured workflow for applying the tools, methods and approaches through the innovation process, and c) a decision-support approach to support interpretation and follow-up actions.

The tools and methods will be structured and mapped following the stage of development of the chemical or material into commercial products (e.g. innovation stage in the stage-gate model, or the Technology Readiness Level). In a first step, the tools will be mapped to two stages: early-stage development and later-stage development.

Input from stakeholders will be gathered to aid in the development and make it fit-for-purpose. To test and gather input for the development of the toolbox case studies will be selected and performed. The case studies will focus on the overall blueprint of the toolbox, the actual functionality but also function as a means to identify gaps e.g. identifying the need for developing additional instruments/tools for the SSbD assessment procedure.

The toolbox will cover both chemicals and materials by addressing the 'by-design' aspect as well as chemical/material use in products. As part of the toolbox, methods will be described for identifying critical properties of chemicals, products, materials, and application processes, such as toxicity, exposure, fate and recyclability, early in the innovation or development process. Using the SSbD toolbox, the "sustainability" requirements can be addressed, taking into account environmental life cycle assessment (LCA), risk assessment and socio-economic assessment methodologies (LCSA). Finally, the toolbox will be available to both regulatory and industrial stakeholders, with the former assessing whether a chemical, material, or product meets the SSbD criteria and the latter using the toolbox to develop chemicals, materials, and products that meet the SSbD criteria at the early stage of innovation or during their development.

2 Existing tools of relevance for the SSbD toolboxes

2.1 Toolbox development methodology

The development of a toolbox is a complex process that comprises of these steps:

- Review of literature on tools, including models, software, methods, methodologies, guidance, toolboxes or databases, on safety and sustainability aspects.

The initial review provides a mapping of existing tools, such as models, methods, and software, and subsequently a gap analysis of tools that are needed at various innovation stages. Further, breakdown of tools in terms of inputs, outputs, underlying models, access rights, etc. provides the basis for the computational architecture of the software.

- Elicitation of stakeholder needs with regard to assessment of SSbD assessment and redesign.

Developing a toolbox should on the one hand be a functional instrument that aids with the assessment of the EU framework but on the other hand be fit for purpose in the sense that it supports the needs of the potential user. The development of the toolbox should therefore go

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hand-in-hand with insight into the actual needs of the stakeholders. This of course is an on-going process, as the toolbox is developed through the project.

Based on an internal literature overview, an assessment of discussion at the JRC/RTD workshop (February 2023), follow-up discussions with companies involved in the case studies, individual company interviews and meetings with representatives of sector organisation we have put together a first overview of potential stakeholder needs and wishes.

2.2 Review methodology and keywords used

The following section provides an overview of the existing tools for safety and sustainability assessment, that can support the PARC SSbD toolbox development. A literature review was conducted to identify the relevant tools for this overview. The review was focused on tools (methods, models, software, toolbox, frameworks, etc.) that have already been developed and are related to safety and sustainability assessment for chemicals and materials. The JRC report on SSbD (Caldeira et al., 2022b) served as the starting point for this review, as it includes a reference to relevant tools for implementing the safety aspect, as well as references to several LCIA methods. Next, by using specific keywords in search engines, such as Scopus and Google Scholar, the review was specifically conducted in two sections, one on safety and the other on sustainability. In addition, several tools were highlighted from previously published inventories such as the OECD SIA Inventory (OECD, 2020b), the OECD Inventory on Exposure Tools (OECD, 2021), and the ISES exposure model inventory (ISES, 2022), as well as from the ECHA Guidance on occupational, consumer and environmental exposure (ECHA, 2016a, ECHA, 2016c, ECHA, 2016b). Aside from the literature review, some of the tools were identified through suggestions provided by partners of the project who have expertise in relevant fields or they have developed their own tools that fit within the framework of SSbD.

Concerning the safety part, the keywords used for the review of the tools related to safety assessment are the following: “Safety AND Assessment AND tools”, “Risk AND Assessment AND tools”, “Hazard AND Assessment AND tools” and “Exposure AND Assessment AND tools”. Regarding the sustainability section, “Sustainability AND Assessment AND tools”, “LCA AND tools” and “LCA AND software” were the main keywords used. A plethora of scientific documents and online resources (grey literature) were retrieved through those searches. The screening of the resulting documents was based on the presence of tools, the availability of related documentation, and the accessibility of those tools. Tools that were no longer available or accessible, as well as tools in development with insufficient results, were excluded from the overview. Moreover, the selection and further assessment of the identified tools was based on the specific predictions that they can provide and how they can serve the scope of the PARC SSbD toolbox. More precisely, the chosen tools were determined by evaluating their alignment with each of the five steps of SSbD and assessing the specific steps that they can effectively cover. Thus, the review concentrated on tools that can cover the following aspects:

- Human health, environmental, and physical hazards of a substance
- Occupational exposure
- Environmental exposure (during the production and the final application)
- Consumer exposure

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- Environmental sustainability
- Socio-economic sustainability

The results of the screening are presented in the figure below. The majority of the tools resulting from this screening are software and models, covering mostly environmental sustainability and exposure assessment (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. The type of assessments the tools cover

2.3 Review of Safe-by-Design (SbD) tools from the nano/advanced materials field

All tool compilations and databases developed for Safe by Design (SbD) in the nano sector have been collected and evaluated here since they can serve in directing the conceptual toolbox design within the project. The source of these studies and literature compiled in Table 1 is primarily recommendations from colleagues and project partners involved in nanosafety-related projects. As internal stakeholders in their respective projects, these colleagues were able to share and provide access to targeted reviews and compilations of SbD tools from the nano sector. Nevertheless, to ensure additional coverage, a literature search on Google Scholar for the keyword 'Safe-by-Design' was carried out which also yielded valuable results.

Such reviews and tool compilations not only serve as a source of prospective tools relevant for inclusion in the PARC toolbox, but they can also inspire the toolbox's conceptual design, i.e. its contents, structure, and user interface. Many past projects have approached toolbox development in diverse ways and all these methodologies need to be better assessed to understand what is relevant for stakeholders of the PARC toolbox. The user interfaces of the preexisting toolboxes, their incorporation of stage-gate, their adherence to SbD principles, along with their strengths and shortcomings should be analyzed and used to inspire the future development of the PARC toolbox and its intricacies. In addition, consideration or not of the stage-gate approach is also outlined. Details on the different models, can be found in the references included in Table 1.

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Table 1. Overview of relevant literature reviewing and compiling SbD tools, frameworks, methods, and literature from (but not necessarily specific to the) nano/advanced materials fields

Reference	Safety Category		Number of Tools	Nature of Review	Consideration of Stage-gate	Incorporating Stakeholder Input	Additional Notes
	Environmental	Human					
(Jeliazkova et al., 2014)	Yes	Yes	104 identified but 34 publicly available	Quantitative: databases are compiled and then linked in order to produce meaningful toxicity estimates	No	Internal stakeholder support to compile databases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funded under eNanoMapper - Toxicological data management of nanomaterials through a computation infrastructure allowing: transparent data sharing, data analysis, and the creation of computational toxicology models - Relevant toxicological databases for chemicals and nanomaterials compiled - Supported include diverse formats (ISA-Tab, OECD Harmonized Templates, custom spreadsheet templates, various databases provided by consortia members)
(RIVM, 2017)	Yes	Yes	24	Not a review but an SbD toolbox	Partially as early, mid, and late development phase	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funded under NanoReg2 - Safe Innovation Approach (SIA) Toolbox - Tools assessing Risks, Costs, and Benefits classified based on product domain (biocides, cosmetics, etc.) and exposure route (dermal, oral or inhalation), which population (consumer, environment, general population or worker), and type of output (qualitative, quantitative, or semi-quantitative)
(Sørensen et al., 2019)	Yes		38	Quantitative: models and tools scored on applicability, resource demands, and outcome parameters	Yes, development of a scoring scheme to assess fitness at each innovation stage	Yes, to determine relevant needs from tools/models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funded under caLIBRAte - Regulators, Industry Associations, Large Enterprises, Consultants, SMEs, and Research Organizations were stakeholders - Environmental Risk Assessment (ERA) Models considered: Material Flow, Fate and Transport, Hazard Assessment, Uptake or Bioavailability, and Risk Assessment Models - Some relevant scoring criteria include time/cost to parameterize and run models, level of required expertise, approval status, availability of guidance, etc.
(Franken et al., 2020)		Yes	17	Quantitative: models were evaluated against relevant compliance	Yes, assessed tools coupled with idea-to-	Yes, to establish 24-compliance criteria for models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funded under caLIBRAte - Study limited to Human Risk Assessment (HRA) tools and assess

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Reference	Safety Category		Number of Tools	Nature of Review	Consideration of Stage-gate	Incorporating Stakeholder Input	Additional Notes
	Environmental	Human					
				criteria established by stakeholders	launch innovation funnel model	at different innovation stages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 19 (including regulators, industry associations, large industries, SMEs, consultants, and research organizations) out of 45 stakeholders provided inputs to this study - Evaluation of models against the following criteria: cost to run the model; maximal duration; market readiness and its validation level; availability of guidance; chemical and toxicological expertise required; etc.
(Nymark et al., 2020)		Yes	50	Qualitative: NAMS have been evaluated in detail against the defined criteria to assess their applicability along stage-gate; however, no scoring has been applied	Yes, "where and how" to apply a NAM along the innovation funnel evaluated	Yes, to establish assessment criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funded under caLIBRAte, Gov4Nano, NanoSolveIT, etc. - 8 NAM categories defined: 1. Searchable databases for grouping and read across purposes; 2. Exposure assessment and modeling; 3. In silico modeling of physicochemical structure and hazard data; 4. In vitro high-throughput and high-content screening assays; 5. Dose-response assessments and modeling; 6. Analyses of biological processes and toxicity pathways; 7. Kinetics and dose extrapolation; 8. Consideration of relevant exposure levels and biomarker endpoints - Assessed NAMS for HRA that address: exposure (7), hazard (24), kinetics (4), and risk (15) - Relevant assessment criteria for NAMs: availability of data, expertise required, quality assessment, etc.
(OECD, 2020a)	Yes	Yes	Around 40	Qualitative: descriptions of all relevant tools and their classification based on respective applications in SbD pillars	Mentioned in the document but the tools are not categorized as per Stage-gate	Yes, to identify barriers to SbD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Report from the OECD proposing the Safe(r) Innovation Approach (SIA) - SbD goes beyond classical RA and aims to achieve safer material with physicochemical structures designed to minimize hazard - Safe material, safer production, safe use, and safe End-of-Life (EoL) are to be considered pillars of SbD, and the evaluated tools have been classified within these pillars - Barriers to SbD based on stakeholder interactions: resources and costs, lack of knowledge, lack of guidance and tools, inadequate regulation, insufficient communication, and challenges to SMEs
(Shandilya and Franken, 2020)	Yes	Yes	160 (93 for nanomaterials, 36 for conventional materials, and remaining for both)	Qualitative: inventory of many nonspecific and other tools that have been mapped and classified based on different criteria; no	Partially applied through the lifecycle model including R&D, development, and use	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gov4Nano deliverable 4.1 - Types (and number) of tools: control banding (5), risk screening (16), life cycle assessment (10), risk evaluation frameworks (19), numerical estimations (50), guidance documents (52), and guidance tools (8) - Evaluation criteria developed: identity, applicability, development state, and regulatory readiness

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Reference	Safety Category		Number of Tools	Nature of Review	Consideration of Stage-gate	Incorporating Stakeholder Input	Additional Notes
	Environmental	Human					
				scoring based on criteria undertaken			Most of the tools in the inventory are quantitative and applicable mostly to chemicals - Numerous tools that consider exposure to industrial workers due to its relevance in the regulatory phase of the innovation value chain
(Falk et al., 2021)	Yes	Yes	28	Qualitative: working descriptions of projects funded under the NanoSafetyCluster (NSC) and Horizon 2020 (NMBP-15 and NMBP-16)	No	Yes, document was created with the voluntary contributions of the project coordinators	- SbD and EU-funded NanoSafety projects document by the NSC - List of relevant policies, standards, labelling schemes, etc. to SbD and nanosafety - List of outcomes (including case studies) from EU projects that support SbD framework
(European Commission et al., 2021)	Yes	Yes	269	Qualitative: summaries of and links to all Horizon 2020 (H2020) projects funded between 2014-2020	No	No	- European research on environment and health: Projects funded by Horizon 2020 (2014-2020) - Working descriptions of all H2020 projects carrying out diverse research: chemical safety and human health; nanosafety and health; air quality and health; urban health; climate change and health; biological safety; environmental and health policymaking; environmental risk factors of health and disease; pollution monitoring and mitigation
(Krans et al., 2021)	Yes	Yes	74	Qualitative: inventory of SbD projects from H2020 funding in Nanotechnology between 2013-2020	No	No	- RIVM's report on H2020 projects on Nanotechnology and SbD - 74 studies subdivided into following themes: research, education, industry, and policy - The description of SbD by the Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management used to select relevant projects - List of projects along with their factsheets and links to project outcomes are available

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Reference	Safety Category		Number of Tools	Nature of Review	Consideration of Stage-gate	Incorporating Stakeholder Input	Additional Notes
	Environmental	Human					
(Joint Research Centre, 2021)	Yes	Yes	Unspecified	Qualitative: repository of all guidance documents, experimental protocols, models, reports, decision support tools, and data management tools along with their descriptions, documented applications, and publications	No	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NANoREG toolbox published as an excel sheet - Regulatory status of tools assessed and defined as: regulatory document, standardized, research product, harmonized or validated - Extensive repository of tools for nanomaterials: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 61 particle size distribution tools • 40 tools on chemical compositions, size, shape, and surface treatment of nanomaterials • 106 tools producing physicochemical, toxicological, ecotoxicological, and environmental fate data required for REACH and chemical safety assessment • 65 in vitro testing, (Q)SARs, Weight of Evidence, grouping, and read-across tools producing data for REACH registration without reliance on animal testing • 20 tools related to identifying the hazards, deriving the DNEL and PNEC values and performing the PBT/vPvB assessment of a nanomaterial according to REACH requirements, and determining the hazard classification and labelling for a nanomaterial according to CLP requirements • 106 tools related to assessing human and environmental exposure to nanomaterials and determining appropriate risk management measures to limit exposures to an acceptable level • 27 tools related to characterizing or managing the risk(s) of nanomaterials according to the REACH procedure or within the REACH regime • 19 tools related to the nonspecific prioritization and risk assessment approach developed in NANoREG, as well as other risk assessment approaches and strategies for nanomaterials that do not necessarily operate within the current REACH regime

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Reference	Safety Category		Number of Tools	Nature of Review	Consideration of Stage-gate	Incorporating Stakeholder Input	Additional Notes
	Environmental	Human					
							<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 16 tools related to managing the risks of nanomaterials by applying the Safe-by-design approach at the research and development stage of nanomaterials and products containing them • 6 tools related to applying the Life Cycle Assessment approach when assessing the risks posed by nanomaterials • 18 tools that help to screen, rank, prioritise, and categorise the risks of nanomaterials and to apply control banding to manage those risks based on minimal information, thus addressing practical (rather than regulatory) risk assessment or management needs <p>- List of all relevant chemical bodies and organizations provided</p>

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Reference	Safety Category		Number of Tools	Nature of Review	Consideration of Stage-gate	Incorporating Stakeholder Input	Additional Notes
	Environmental	Human					
(Shandilya et al., 2021)	Yes	Yes	14	Quantitative: Transparency, Reliability, Accessibility, Applicability, and Completeness (TRAAC) assessment framework applied to tools	Partially incorporated through scoring in the "applicable lifecycle stages" criteria under the Applicability pillar; direct reference to stage-gate absent	Yes, through a workshop to present the TRAAC framework and also refine it	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TRAAC framework (preprint) funded under Gov4Nano - Aim is to assess regulatory acceptance, downstream use by different stakeholders, and hindrances to the same - Workshop stakeholders included researchers, academics, industry, regulators, consultants, and government from the EU - Five TRAAC Pillars: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Transparency: Ownership, clear communication about development, methods, strengths, and limitations (i.e. boundary of use); 2. Reliability: Quality, correctness, and consistency of output; 3. Accessibility: Usability, findability, and user experience evaluation; 4. Applicability: Applicability domain and adequacy to address user need(s); 5. Completeness: Comprehensiveness in regard to EU regulatory frameworks and requirements for MNMs.
(European Commission et al., 2022b, European Commission et al., 2022a)	Yes	Yes	119 frameworks reviewed	Qualitative: compilation of all relevant literature pertinent to Safe- and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) including industry standards, compliance documents, methods, models, tools, etc.	Both lifecycle and stage-gate are central to SSbD but the proposed frameworks have only been partially assessed for the same	Planned incorporation in future reports (Case Study reports)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SSbD reports from JRC including the framework, along with the review methods, indicators, and tools - Sectors considered: Chemicals, Products (cosmetics, electronics, etc.), Materials (nanomaterials, plastics, textiles, etc.), and Services - Origin of the frameworks could be from Academia, Industry, NGOs, Legislation or proposals, International organizations, and Certification bodies - Hierarchical and scoring methods for SSbD evaluation described

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Reference	Safety Category		Number of Tools	Nature of Review	Consideration of Stage-gate	Incorporating Stakeholder Input	Additional Notes
	Environmental	Human					
(Guinée et al., 2022)	Yes	Yes	19	Qualitative review of SbD and SSbD literature to assess consistency in the definition of lifecycles	No, but lifecycle is a central theme	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SbD and lifecycles review - Assesses the consistency in the definitions and terms used by SbD literature - Focus on distinguishing definitions and lifecycles of products, materials, and chemicals - Identifies the following 3 relevant lifecycles: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Product lifecycle 2. Chemical lifecycle in a specific product or material 3. Chemical lifecycle in all possible product or material applications
(Furxhi et al., 2023)				Qualitative review of 11 relevant EU projects and how they meet SSbD requirements foreseen by stakeholders	No	Yes, reports the answers and opinions from stakeholder workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funded under DIAGONAL, HARMLESS, SUNSHINE, NanoFabNet, ASINA, SAbyNA, RiskGone, SbD4Nano, SABYDOMA, and IRISS - Highlights the relevant industrial topics along with technical and organizational challenges to SSbD - Discussion on key feedback from stakeholders relating to: Industrial targeted sectors, SSbD framework, lifecycles, FAIR data, business models, missing knowledge, certifications, challenges, and future goals
(Ruijter et al., 2023)		Yes	20	Qualitative: in vitro assays for hazard testing have been evaluated against specific criteria to understand suitability for SbD	Partially, as the methods have been assessed on the basis of their prediction accuracy for early hazard warning; so the early-phase 'by-design' concept has been adhered to strongly	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funded under SAbyNA - Hazard testing assays (and number) evaluated: Cytotoxicity (5), dissolution (3), oxidative potential (4), inflammation (4), and genotoxicity (4) - Evaluation criteria for assays: predictive, simple and cost-effective, robust, compatible, and readiness - Challenges posed by in Vitro Testing NMs for SbD Applicability identified: Influence of Medium Components; Determining Dose Delivered to Cells; SbD Hazard Testing of NMs Released during the Life Cycle; Feasibility and Relevance
(Subramanian et al., 2023)	Yes	Yes	12	Qualitative: review of literature presenting approaches to combine Lifecycle Assessment	Yes, the assessment particularly focuses on and attempts to reconcile the TRL and	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funded by the Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management and under BALIHT

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Reference	Safety Category		Number of Tools	Nature of Review	Consideration of Stage-gate	Incorporating Stakeholder Input	Additional Notes
	Environmental	Human					
				(LCA) and RA approaches at lower Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) and describes them against defined criteria	stage-gate models to see the applicability of proposed LCA+RA approaches		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Criteria used to describe LCA+RA approaches: TRL, application domain, SbD focus, RA approach, LC approach, Technology System, and System Boundaries - Advantages and disadvantages in the context of product design have also been evaluated
(NanoSolveIT, 2023)	Yes	Yes	7	Qualitative: compilation of tools developed in NanoSolveIT project	No	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funded under NanoSolveIT - In silico Integrated Approach to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for the environmental health and safety of nanomaterials (ENM), implemented through a decision support system packaged as both stand-alone open software and via a Cloud platform - Compilation of tools capable of: omics data preprocessing, zeta potential calculation, cytotoxicity prediction, prediction of exposure effects on Daphnia Magna, visualization for IATA, and organizing gene annotations in experiments
(caLIBRATE and Gov4Nano, 2023)	Yes	Yes	35 (including regulations, guidance documents, etc.)	Qualitative: repository of nano-risk governance tools compiled into a platform of tools	Yes, the objective is to provide a stage-gate nano-risk governance guidance approach	Compilation of tools developed by internal project stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - caLIBRAte x Gov4Nano Nano-Risk Governance Platform (under development) - Library containing information on nanotechnology, relevant regulations (4), guidance documents (8), tools (20), and data libraries (3) - Domains covered: governance, risk scoping, data, worker, consumer, exposure, environment, characterization, toxicological testing, SbD, and sustainability - Description of nano-risk governance framework as per ISO 21505

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2.3.1 Nature of Review

Just like the tools they review, the studies and literature compiled within this assessment have been classified as either quantitative or qualitative. Qualitative reviews typically compile a repository of tools with their descriptions and classify the tools based on function. By providing information on coverage and shortcomings of the reviewed tools, these qualitative reviews are critical in broadly identifying sectoral needs: in what direction future development of tools should be targeted? And for which specific function or application is the future development of tools necessary? For example, Subramanian et al., (2023), through their quantitative assessment of the available SbD tools combining RA and lifecycle methods, highlight that further refinement of SbD tools is necessary so that these tools can model meaningful results for scaled-up systems which are relevant, particularly at later stages of the stage-gate. Similarly, Nymark et al., (2020) evaluate 50 NAMs and deduce that they offer extensive opportunities for HRA during the innovation stage and identify the following factors to improve the value proposition of NAMS: increased availability of safety data, reduction in uncertainty of exposure potential, better understanding and modelling of toxicological pathways, availability of data, etc. Additionally, Krans et al., (2021) qualitatively diagnose that more case studies are required to test the application of tools developed within EU projects as currently, the dearth of such industrial case studies raises questions on the robustness and applicability of these tools. On the other hand, Ruijter et al., (2023) qualitatively assess and identify several cell assays that can serve as early hazard assessment systems, especially after their testing and validation for standardization. Guinée et al., (2022) qualitatively check the consistency in the definitions of common terms used in SbD studies and proposes alignment measures for the same. Both, the European Commission et al., (2021) and Falk et al., (2021) describe in detail all relevant projects and work carried out with EU funding and plans for future research. Apart from published review papers and reports, repositories of tools such as the SIA toolbox (RIVM, 2017), Nanoreg toolbox (Joint Research Centre, 2021), and Gov4Nano Deliverable (Shandilya and Franken, 2020) have also been classified as qualitative reviews. All these repositories are quite extensive and detailed and within the repositories, tools have been compiled and categorized based on usage and origin. These tool repositories do not score, rank or rate the tools, yet they provide valuable insights to the trends in SbD tools and the gaps in the availability of tools. In particular, Shandilya & Franken (2020) review 160 tools (applicable for both nanomaterials as well as conventional materials) to assess their nature and origin, data accessibility, sectoral and industrial applicability, along with the ability to meet regulatory acceptance, etc. Hence, such qualitative reviews (including reviews publications and repositories) offer a foray into SbD research by painting a general landscape of available tools in broad strokes.

Figure 4. Methodology applied for a quantitative review of HRA models as implemented by Franken et al., (2020)

Table 2. Quantitative scoring of the models undertaken by Sørensen et al., (2019) and the corresponding scoresheet assessing the relevance of different ERA models at different stages in the stage-gate model

Environmental assessment model		Reference	Idea	Scope	Business case	R&D	Test & validate	Launch	Monitor
Maternal flow	PMFA	35	1	2	2	8	14	16	13
	PMFA version 1.0.0	34	4	8	13	18	23	18	16
	DPMFA	36	1	2	2	9	15	17	14
	Spatial-PMFA	37	1	2	2	8	12	14	12
	MFA	38	2	5	10	13	22	17	14
	Tiede et al. 2010	39	3	2	5	9	14	12	10
	LearNano	40	2	4	10	12	18	15	12
Fate	SimpleBox4Nano	14	4	9	15	18	22	17	14
	NanoDUFLOW	41	2	2	4	9	15	12	11
	Rhine model	11	2	2	4	8	14	11	9
	MendNano	42	1	2	2	7	12	14	11
	WSM/WASP7	43	1	2	2	7	13	15	12
	Rhone model	44	2	2	4	8	14	11	9
	RedNano	45	1	2	2	8	13	15	12
	GWAVA with water quality module	46, 47	2	2	4	9	14	12	10
Hazard	US EPA SSD generator	48, 49	2	4	9	13	21	17	14
	SSWD	10	1	1	2	8	13	14	12
	NanoQSAR model	50, 51	7	8	12	14	14	11	9
	Framework for oxidative stress potential	52	8	7	6	10	9	6	4
	nanoSAR	53	4	5	6	10	9	6	4
	nano-SAR (OCHEM, WEKA)	54	2	2	5	9	13	10	8
	Nanoprofiler 1.2	55	2	2	4	9	13	10	8
Uptake	Kinetic model/BCF	56	6	11	16	17	16	12	10
	Two component efflux/uptake model	57	6	11	16	17	16	12	10
	Biodynamic model	58	6	11	16	17	16	12	10
	BLM concept model	59	6	11	16	17	16	12	10
Risk	FINE	60	6	6	8	12	14	15	13
	Precautionary matrix for synthetic nanomaterials	8	22	20	19	17	13	14	13
	Tervonen et al. 2009	61	8	9	15	16	18	14	13
	SUN, 2016	34	7	8	14	20	27	23	21
	pERA	13	6	6	9	16	20	21	19
	LICARA nanoSCAN	9	9	11	14	16	16	13	11
	nanoinfo	62	6	6	10	17	25	22	19
	Topuz and van Gestel, 2016	63	5	6	8	16	19	20	18
	GUIDEnano tool	None	6	6	10	18	26	22	20
	SUNDS 2nd tier	None	5	5	9	17	25	22	20
	SUNDS 1st tier	9	9	11	14	16	16	13	11
	GUIDEnano tool intermediate	None	8	11	18	23	28	23	21

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In contrast to qualitative reviews, quantitative ones not only compile but also study individual tools and score, rate, or rank them on the basis of certain parameters. An example of the methodology used in a quantitative study has been sourced from Franken et al., (2020) and is depicted in Figure 4: Franken et al., (2020) compile a repository of tools and then assess them against certain criteria defined and weighted by the selected stakeholders of the study. The resulting scores from the application of the methodology depicted in Figure 4 could be represented as per

Figure 4. Methodology applied for a quantitative review of HRA models as implemented by Franken et al., (2020)

Table 2: Sørensen et al., (2019) score the fitness of the assessed tools at each stage of the innovation process. Quantitative reviews, by focusing on individual tools and their respective details, could offer a higher resolution output that may not be captured in solely qualitative assessments. For example, the quantitative TRAAC assessment undertaken by Shandilya et al., (2021) quantitatively bolsters the findings of Krans et al., (2021), by showing that the limited number of application case studies results in a lower reliability score for the tools; coupling the lower reliability score with the limited availability of early-stage data hinders the regulatory applicability of the tools. Therefore, the quantitative assessments identified in this study adeptly assess the operability and application potential of specific tools. The 'deep-dive' nature of quantitative assessments implies a more detailed assessment of individual tools at the cost of efforts; hence, seemingly quantitative reviews assess a smaller set of tools due to the high level of comprehensiveness required. Finally, although both kinds of assessments are valuable for practitioners, their inherent outputs are different. Qualitative reviews assist in creating a 'bird's-eye view' of the tool landscape and future tool needs. Whereas, quantitative reviews manage to assess finer aspects of individual tools such as the possibilities of refinement and persistent data challenges.

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2.3.2 Incorporating Stakeholder Input

Although not implemented universally in reviews, stakeholder feedback is critical in providing direction for the future development of both tools and procurement of data (Soeteman-Hernandez et al., 2019, Soeteman-Hernández et al., 2021). Studies identify multiple internal and external stakeholders ranging from academics to industry experts and regulators. Internal stakeholders, such as EU-project coordinators, provide pertinent feedback on the methodology and goals of tool development processes as they typically have the best overview and understand how to translate the developments into meaningful outputs (Falk et al., 2021). External stakeholder feedback in quantitative review studies (Franken et al., 2020, Shandilya et al., 2021, Sørensen et al., 2019) mainly served two purposes: development of the criteria, scoring scheme, and weights for the assessment; or scoring tools within the predefined scoring framework.

Apart from the direct influence on results, external stakeholders' feedback also provides valuable insights. External stakeholders in Sørensen et al., (2019) study underscored the importance of simplicity (and low expertise requirement) and fast run times for early-stage ERA models. Furthermore, the stakeholders demand that ERA models should identify potential hazards, offer risk management measures, and offer regulatory compliance functionality. Similarly, for HRA models assessed by Franken et al., (2020), the stakeholders wanted the tools to be differentiated according to their applicability in the innovation stages. The needs of stakeholders from the tools also differed depending on the innovation stage: early-stage tools should be fast to run, cheap to operate, and require a low level of expertise to provide qualitative output in the format of classes/control bands; whereas, later-stage HRA models should provide quantitative outputs. Irrespective of the application phase, stakeholders of the HRA tools also preferred their acceptance by regulatory authorities. Hence stakeholder feedback is necessary and can shed light on issues that can particularly challenge the widespread use of tools such as requirements of specific functionality, user-friendliness, training requirements, compliance needs, and regulatory acceptance (Nymark et al., 2020, Shandilya et al., 2021). Additionally, OECD (2020a) reports barriers to the operationalization of SSbD (and the corresponding toolboxes) based on stakeholder interactions: high resources and costs, lack of knowledge, lack of guidance documents, inadequate regulation, insufficient communication, and challenging adoption by SMEs.

The origin of stakeholders is an important factor in the quality of feedback received in a study. For example, stakeholders belonging to regulatory bodies, may not be able to answer questions about model kinetics in detail Sørensen et al., (2019). Similarly, stakeholders originating from different sectors will report different priorities based on the needs of their respective sectors (for example, textiles versus electronics) (Furxhi et al., 2023). Nevertheless, approaching a diverse pool of stakeholders is recommended as incorporating diverse feedback and viewpoints in any assessment will be conducive to its quality and coverage of topics for discussions. In this context, following the FAIR principles both with regard to modeling and to data usage is essential. If data/models are FAIR they come with rich metadata and metadata is needed for stakeholders to identify data that is relevant for them. In essence it is all about annotation with the correct terminology/structured vocabularies/ontologies in order to allow the stakeholder to find the right data.

2.3.3 Consideration of the stage-gate

The stage-gate model (Cooper, 1990, Brillhuis-Meijer et al., 2016) is depicted in Figure 5 and it represents the various process steps involved in the chemical and material innovation process. Assessing the applicability of the tools at individual phases within the stage-gate model is relevant for SSbD since a key identifier of SSbD tools is their applicability at early stages of innovation i.e. during the design stage. Many

reviews compiled in safe-by-design assessment thus far do not incorporate the stage-gate model in their review and may therefore be misclassifying compliance tools, applicable at later stages of the innovation process, as SSbD tools. Without factoring in the stage gate, it is challenging to identify SSbD tools that inherently meet the 'by-design' requirement and distinguish them from ones that are fundamentally suited for compliance assessment due to their high requirement of data and resource inputs.

Figure 5. The stage-gate model and the different requirements at each stage defined by the stakeholders as described in Sørensen et al., (2019)

The SIA Toolbox (RIVM, 2017), classifies tools based on their applicability in their innovation phase as either early potential, mid indicator, or demonstrator. As depicted in Figure 6, the user of the SIA Toolbox can specify the phase of innovation for which an assessment tool is required, and the toolbox accordingly yields the relevant tools addressing the risks, costs, benefits, or a combination of these elements. Although the incorporation of the detailed stage-gate model is exempted from the SIA Toolbox, nevertheless the former's essence is preserved as the toolbox can distinguish early-phase tools that are suitable for SSbD applications. Ruijter et al., (2023) also do not wholly employ the stage-gate model in their assessment but by focusing on the applicability during the early-innovation phase, they have identified the potential of simpler cell assays in raising early-stage hazard warning for multiple toxicological endpoints thereby serving the aim of SbD hazard testing.

Both quantitative reviews (Franken et al., 2020, Sørensen et al., 2019) from the caLIBRAte project apply the stage-gate model for the assessment of specific tools. As shown in

Figure 4. Methodology applied for a quantitative review of HRA models as implemented by Franken et al., (2020)

Table 2, Sørensen et al., (2019) have assessed various models and each of their applicability at individual gates of the stage-gate model and they identify that most ERA models perform similarly at the same gate. A key reason for this is the complexity of these models and their increased efficiency at later stages of innovation when the amount of information, resource, and expertise allocated to product development is automatically higher. However, at earlier innovation stages the ERA models receive a poorer score than at the later gates as shown in

Figure 4. Methodology applied for a quantitative review of HRA models as implemented by Franken et al., (2020)

Table 2. It is therefore important to accordingly refine the ERA tools so that they are suitable also at early stages and can operate with limited data and resources. In contrast, Franken et al., (2020) found the HRA models (despite having similar limitations to ERA models, i.e. requiring a high level of expertise and resources) showing variable levels of fitness at different gates, i.e. instead of all models being suitable for later stages, some models were better at earlier stages, whereas others at mid-stages; two HRA models were found to be equally suitable and applicable for all gates. Similarly, Nymark et al., (2020) found that 37 of the 50 NAMs reviewed were well applicable to the stage-gate innovation model for human safety assessments.

Figure 6. User input interface from the SIA Toolbox (RIVM, 2017) that accepts the product development phase as an input query to yield relevant tools addressing the risks, costs, benefits, or a combination of these elements

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One interesting trend observed between reviews is the mutual exclusivity of the stage-gate model and lifecycle models in the assessments. For example, reviews either focus on the classification of tools based on stage-gate or their applicability in different lifecycle phases (production, use, or End-of-life). For example, Shandilya et al., (2021) in the assessment incorporate the different lifecycle stages (i.e. R&D/Synthesis, Manufacturing, Use, and End-of-life) while directly referencing the stage-gate (but it may be argued that they include the stage-gate by proxy in the R&D scoring). This is likely attributable to the fact that traditionally, the stage-gate model could only encompass the production and use phase, and the incorporation of End-of-life is a novel and still seldom phenomenon in product design (Favi et al., 2017). Therefore, further reconciliation of the stage-gate model and lifecycle thinking approach is necessary for the development and classification of relevant SSbD tools (Guinée et al., 2022); the OECD's SSIA (OECD, 2020a) approach is attempting to do the same.

2.4 Overview of existing tools for Safety and Sustainability assessment

In the context of this overview, several tools have been identified, both for safety and sustainability assessment. As previously stated, the tools were chosen based on the needs of SSbD in terms of predictions and data; the emphasis was on tools that could serve each step of the SSbD framework. In more detail, the tools were classified as safety and sustainability assessment tools according to their functionality and estimates. The safety assessment tools were divided into the following three categories: exposure, hazard, and risk assessment. These tools can contribute to the estimation of the releases of chemicals to the environment (e.g. STAN or PMFA, EUSES), chemical exposure in the general population (e.g. INTEGRA, ConsExpo, MERLIN-Expo) as well as in workplaces (e.g. ECETOC TRA, ART, EMKG-Expo Tool). Furthermore, tools that aid in the identification of hazardous chemicals (e.g. GreenScreen for Safer Chemicals, OECD QSAR Toolbox, AMBIT, VEGA, Danish (Q)SAR Database), as well as tools for chemical risk assessment (e.g. Chesar, INTEGRA), are very critical. In terms of sustainability assessment tools, several LCIA methods (e.g. USEtox, Environmental Footprint method, LC-Impact, IMPACT World+, ReCiPe), as well as software for LCA (GaBi, openLCA, SimaPro, Umberto, Brightway2) were identified. Finally, methodologies for the implementation of Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) (Portfolio Sustainability Assessment, Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment) are also included. All of the aforementioned tools are briefly presented in the following sections.

2.4.1 Tools for Safety Assessment

2.4.1.1 Tools for Exposure Assessment

Based on the previously described tool review, the identified exposure assessment tools are listed in the following table (Table 3). More specifically, the tools for exposure assessment are:

- **Advanced REACH Tool (ART):** Advanced REACH tool (ART) v1.5 is an exposure assessment tool that estimates occupational inhalation exposure to dust, mist, and vapour based on a source-receptor approach (Cherrie and Schneider, 1999, Tielemans et al., 2008b). It defines nine principal modifying factors (MF), including activity emission potential, substance emission potential, localized control and segregation. It is a tier 2 exposure model, based on activity-specific exposures and divided into near-field (within 1 m in any direction of the worker's head) and far-field compartments (the remainder of the workplace) (Fransman et al., 2011). ART provides exposure estimates and confidence intervals for

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different percentiles, for full-shift and long-term exposures. It is a web-based tool that employs a mechanistic model and an empirical component that includes information from an exposure database.

- **APEX:** The Air Pollutants Exposure Model (APEX) is an inhalation exposure model, derived from the probabilistic NAAQS Exposure Model and aligned to the Total Risk Integrated Methodology (TRIM) model framework (EPA, 2022a). The aim of APEX is to suggest new solutions for the protection of vulnerable groups' health, improve existing solutions and reduce adverse outcomes. It merges three urban models of air pollution, to estimate citizens' exposure to air pollution. These three models are for buildings, for urban form and a human behavior model (EPA, 2022a, R&I, 2022). APEX uses a database of personal exposure measurements reported at different research campaign publications (EPA, 2022a). APEX is applied at local, and urban scale and simulates human exposure to several pollutants through time and space (e.g., outdoors and indoors) (R&I, 2022).
- **ChemSTEER:** ChemSTEER v3.2 is a computer-based assessment tool for estimating occupational exposures and environmental releases. It was developed by the US Environmental Protection Agency's Office of Pollution Prevention and Toxics (OPPT) as a screening tool for detecting potential chemical exposure in the workplace, as well as an estimation tool for dermal and inhalation exposures. In addition, ChemSTEER offers information and estimation techniques for estimating chemical use in typical industrial sectors. It does not, however, include methods for estimating the exposure of consumers or the general public to chemicals. ChemSTEER is a tool designed for assessing potential risks and exposures linked to chemicals, as well as for assessing new chemicals (EPA, 2015a, EPA, 2015b).
- **Consumer Exposure Model (CEM):** Consumer Exposure Model (CEM) v2.1 is an exposure assessment model developed by the Office of Pollution Prevention and Toxics (OPPT) of the US EPA that estimates indoor air and dust concentrations, as well as dermal and oral exposure to new and existing chemicals in consumer products and articles. It includes 53 product categories, 20 article categories, 11 generic product categories and one generic article category. CEM was originally part of the E-FAST model and the updated version 2.1 includes the existing models of E-FAST and 15 additional models. More specifically, there are 6 emission models, 3 inhalation models, 5 ingestion models and 7 dermal models (ICF, 2019).
- **ConsExpo:** ConsExpo (short for Consumer Exposure) is a tool developed by the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM). ConsExpo is a risk assessment tool that provides quantitative exposure evaluations for chemicals found in consumer items. It is used to calculate and quantify consumer exposure to chemicals found in a variety of consumer items. ConsExpo includes exposure models for inhalation, dermal contact, and oral exposure. To estimate chemical exposure, this model considers a variety of criteria such as user characteristics, exposure situations, and product usage habits. It also contains pre-programmed settings for a variety of consumer products, such as cleaning chemicals and personal care items (Delmaar and Schuur, 2017b).
- **CONTAM:** CONTAM was developed at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). It is a multizone indoor air quality and ventilation analysis computer program that has various applications and is able to determine airflow rates and pressure between zones of the building, to predict contaminant concentrations and exposure of inhabitants to airborne pollutants. CONTAM can find various applications based on its ability to calculate building airflow rates and pressures between zones of the building. CONTAM is able to predict the exposure of occupants to airborne contaminants for

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eventual risk assessment. At last, CONRAM can be used for the design and analysis of smoke management systems in the interior of buildings (NIST, 2021).

- **DPMFA:** DPMFA stands for Dynamic Probabilistic Material Flow Analysis and is a code developed by Empa in Switzerland. DPMFA is a tool for performing a dynamic material flow analysis allowing full consideration of parameter uncertainty. It allows to study and analyze the movement and transformation of chemicals and materials over time within a system or a particular geographical area. It provides a systematic framework for assessing the input, output, and stocks of substances in various stages of production, consumption, and waste management. DPMFA focuses on understanding the entire life cycle of substances, including extraction, production, distribution, use, and disposal and is able to quantify releases to environmental compartments over time.
- **ECETOC TRA:** The ECETOC TRA v3.1 was developed by ECETOC and estimates the risk of chemical exposure for workers, consumers, and the environment. It is a tier 1 screening model and consists of three main components; workers, consumers, and the environment, where for each of them there is a separate exposure estimation model. The tool considers different exposure scenarios and it can provide occupational and consumer exposure and risk estimates for inhalation, dermal and oral exposure routes. It is a user-friendly designed tool that can be used for screening assessment. Lastly, it is integrated into the Chesar (Chemical Safety Assessment and Reporting) tool as part of the occupational and consumer exposure assessment (ECETOC, 2012).
- **E-FAST:** The Exposure and Fate Assessment Screening Tool (E-FAST) calculates the concentrations of chemical releases in the atmosphere, landfills, rivers, lakes, streams, and consumer goods. It calculates the yearly number of days that aquatic ecotoxicological concentrations are surpassed, as well as proper human dose rates for several routes of chemical exposure. By choosing which exposure modules to run, the user can determine what physicochemical and fate data is needed (EPA, 2022b). Another application of E-FAST is the assessment of chemical inhalation and dermal exposures resulting from the use of certain consumer products. It evaluates exposed populations as either a subset of the general population or consumers and includes default exposure parameter values. The model does not assess worker exposure. E-FAST exposure estimates take into account the levels of substances that are inhaled, ingested, or applied topically to the skin. Finally, E-FAST does not calculate chemical absorption, fate parameters, or physicochemical properties (Versar Inc., 2007).
- **EMKG-Expo-Tool:** The EMKG-Expo-Tool approach (“Easy-to-use workplace control scheme for hazardous substances” (EMKG)) is an exposure assessment tool that uses a control banding approach based on COSHH Essentials to estimate occupational inhalation exposure to hazardous substances. It is a Tier 1 assessment tool, easy to use, providing quantitative occupational exposure assessment. EMKG-Expo-Tool estimates exposure to a substance based on its amount used and its volatility/dustiness, as well as on its control strategy. Based on the ECHA Guidance R.14 (ECHA, 2016a), it can be viewed as a means of filtering out workplace situations that do not pose a risk from those that need further analysis (BAuA, 2018).
- **EPA ExpoBox:** EPA ExpoBox (EXPOsure toolbox) is developed by the US EPA and is a toolbox containing guidance, databases and models related to chemical exposure assessment. It has an easy-to-use interface that guides the assessor through the assessment and provides links to several models, guidance, databases, or frameworks relevant to human exposure.

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- **Long range Research Initiative Toolbox:** The Long Rang Research Initiative (LRI) toolbox includes state-of-the-art and user-friendly tools for chemical risk assessment and toxicity testing that benefit industry, academia, and regulatory agencies. It is divided into three different categories, including Human Health Database (such as FedTex, DTOX, RepDose), Human Health Models (such as AMBIT, INTEGRA, ART) and Environmental Models (such as GREATER 4.0, GUTS, BAT).
- **MERLIN-Expo Tool:** MERLIN-Expo v4.0 (Modelling Exposure to chemicals for Risk assessment: a comprehensive Library of multimedia and PBPK models for Integration, Prediction, uNcertainty and Sensitivity analysis) is an exposure assessment software that includes a library of multimedia and PBPK models for human and environmental exposure to chemicals. MERLIN-Expo was developed as part of the 4FUN project and is based on the prototype 2-FUN tool. By using Merlin-Expo, simulations can be performed both deterministically and probabilistically. As part of the software, multimedia, and PBPK models are integrated, and all aspects of exposure assessment are taken into account, from the environment to the internal human body tissues. The model encompasses lifetime risk for various human populations, taking into account exposure via multiple routes. MERLIN-Expo includes a library of sub-systems that the user can utilize to perform a specific scenario (Merlin-Expo, 2017).
- **PMFA:** PMFA stands for Probabilistic Material Flow Analysis and is a code developed by Empa in Switzerland. PMFA is a material flow analysis tool that allows full consideration of parameter uncertainty. PMFA allows to study and analyze the movement and transformation of chemicals and materials within a system or a particular geographical area. It provides a systematic framework for assessing the input and output of substances in various stages of production, consumption, and waste management. PMFA focuses on understanding the entire life cycle of substances, including extraction, production, distribution, use, and disposal.
- **SimpleBox:** SimpleBox is a multimedia mass balance model following the “Mackay type”. Its principal application lies in examining and predicting environmental fate based on fundamental physical and chemical substance properties. More specifically, it models the environmental fate of chemicals by representing them as fluxes (mass flows) between a sequence of well-mixed boxes incorporating several environmental compartments (air, water, sediment and soil) at regional, continental and global spatial scales. SimpleBox takes user-specified release rates as input and generates exposure concentrations in the environment as output. It calculates mass flow rates based on the physical and chemical properties of the substances, as well as the features of the environment being modelled (RIVM, 2022a).
- **SprayExpo:** SprayExpo 2.3 is a model, developed by BAuA that estimates the occupational inhalation and dermal exposure to aerosols through spray applications of non-volatile biocidal substances. It calculates the concentrations of meaningful particle size fractions of aerosols to determine inhalation and dermal exposure. Additionally, the model incorporates gravitational settling, turbulent spray mixing, and droplet evaporation. SprayExpo is an MS Excel worksheet that offers a freely selectable scenario as well as three different predefined scenarios, including spraying of antifouling paints, spraying along a line on the wall and room spraying by fogging/misting (BAuA, 2017).
- **STAN:** STAN (subSTance flow ANalysis) is a freeware designed to facilitate material flow analysis. STAN is a tool that helps to perform material flow analysis. STAN enables the building of graphical models by using predefined components (processes, flows, system boundaries, text fields). After the input or import of known data (mass flows, stocks, concentrations, transfer coefficients) for different layers (good, substance, energy) and periods, unknown quantities can be computed. STAN can address the first part

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of exposure assessment by calculating mass flows through society and releases into technical or natural compartments. Its output can be used by environmental fate software as input.

- **TREXMO & TREXMO+:** TRAnslation of EXposure MOdels or TREXMO developed by the Institute for Work and Health (IST), is an interface tool with six existing regulatory occupational exposure models (EASE, EMKG-Expo Tool, MEASE, ECETOC TRA, Stoffenmanager, and Advanced REACH Tool (ART)), which are not fully independent. The tool connects the exposure models to support more reliable parameter selection and safer exposure/risk assessments. TREXMO can provide exposure estimates. TREXMO+ is a machine-learning technique in R language (version 3.5.0) for exposure data, developed based on the inter-model translations that already existed from TREXMO. Its principal is to split the data into subsets, according to exposure conditions with similar characteristics. In comparison with TREXMO, TREXMO+ uses only three REACH models, ART, Stoffenmanager, and ECETOC TRAv3 (Savic et al., 2020).
- **Vermeer FCM:** VERMEER FCM is a risk assessment software for chemicals used in plastic Food Contact Materials (FCM), developed within the VERMEER project and integrated into the Merlin-Expo-Tool. Based on the contact time and temperature, the material type, the food, and the physicochemical properties of the chemicals, the tool can estimate the concentration of migrating chemicals from contact with FCM. The publicly accessible software was created under the FCM regulatory framework (Regulation EU No 10/2011). The toxicological data requirements for plastic FCM compounds are defined by the compound's migration into food. VERMEER FCM predicts chemical migration in food in interaction with plastic Food Contact Materials (FCM), as well as numerous toxicological outcomes (LIFE VERMEER, 2022).

Table 3. Tools for Exposure Assessment

Tools	Description	Type of tool (method, model, software, etc.)	Link
Advanced REACH Tool (ART)	A tool that estimates occupational inhalation exposure based on a source-receptor approach	Software	URL°
APEX	A tool that simulates human inhalation exposure to several pollutants, both outdoors and indoors	Model	URL°
CEM	A tool that incorporates models, databases, use scenarios and methods to estimate Inhalation, Non-Dietary Ingestion and Dermal exposure.	Software	URL°
ChemSTEER	A tool that assesses occupational exposure to chemicals, as well as environmental releases	Software	URL°
CONTAM	A tool for estimation of airflows, contaminant concentrations and personal exposure to air borne contaminants	Software	URL°
ConsExpo	A consumer exposure assessment tool, estimating the dermal, inhalation, and ingestion exposures of consumers to substances	Model	URL°
DPMFA	A tool to perform dynamic probabilistic materials flow analysis	Software	URL°
ECETOC TRA	A tool that estimates the risk of chemical exposure for workers, consumers, and the environment.	Model	URL°
E-FAST	An exposure and fate assessment tool, which calculates the concentrations of chemicals releases in	Software	URL°

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	the atmosphere, landfills, rivers, lakes, streams, and consumer goods		
EMKG-Expo-Tool 2.0	A tool that estimates occupational exposure to hazardous substances using a control banding approach	Software	URL°
EPA ExpoBox	A toolbox that includes guidance, databases and models for exposure assessment for the below categories: Approaches, Media, Routes, Tiers, and Types, Life stages and Populations, Chemical Classes	Toolbox	URL°
Long range Research Initiative Toolbox	A toolbox that includes state-of-the-art and easy-to-use tools for chemical risk assessment and toxicity testing.	Toolbox	URL°
MERLIN-Expo tool	An exposure assessment software including a library of models for human and environmental exposure to chemicals	Software	URL°
PMFA	A tool to perform probabilistic materials flow analysis	Software	URL°
SimpleBox	A multimedia mass balance model that estimates the environmental fate of chemicals	Model	URL°
SprayExpo	A tool that estimates the occupational inhalation and dermal exposure to aerosols through spray applications	Model	URL°
STAN	A tool to perform material flow analysis (MFA) to quantify flows of materials/chemicals through society and into the environment	Software	URL*
TREXMO & TREXMO+	An occupational exposure assessment tool, which incorporates six models and enables their simultaneous use	Model	URL°
VERMEER FCM	A risk assessment software for chemicals used in plastic Food Contact Materials (FCM)	Software	URL°

2.4.1.2 Tools for Hazard Assessment

A number of hazard assessment tools were identified as a result of the conducted review of tools. These tools are described and listed (Table 4) below:

- AMBIT Tool:** AMBIT is an open-source chemoinformatic tool developed by Cefic-LRI to aid businesses in the assessment of chemical safety. In AMBIT, users can have access to a database with more than 450.000 chemicals and a dataset containing 14.570 REACH substances. It assists companies in complying with chemical regulations, which leads to safer chemical use and lower testing and innovation costs (AMBIT, 2018). AMBIT is based on a 'predictive toxicity model' and it employs read-across and categorization principles (Kunz and Hubesch, 2016). It contains several in-silico prediction models, such as Toxtree, and can produce both molecular descriptors and structure alerts. AMBIT data is used to create comprehensive read-across and category definition assessment workflows (AMBIT, 2018).
- ChemCOACH:** ChemCoach is an approach by ChemSec that assists companies in integrating the chemical safety of their products. It is focused particularly on chemicals that have been recognized as endocrine disruptors (EDCs). It is a four-step approach that guides companies in the identification and replacement of safer alternatives of EDCs in their products.

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- **ChemFORWARD Safer:** ChemFORWARD SAFER is a tool that assists individual suppliers in identifying safer ingredients to ensure human and environmental safety. It includes safer alternatives for chemicals using their trade name by utilizing the available hazard assessments in the ChemFORWARD platform. The safer ingredients are arranged by their CAS number, trade name, function, application, etc. ChemFORWARD SAFER is applicable to chemicals that are naturally or synthetically derived or polymers (ChemFORWARD, 2023).
- **Danish (Q)SAR Database:** The Danish (Q)SAR database, developed by the DTU National Food Institute, is an inventory of QSAR models for searching hazardous chemical properties (physicochemical properties, environmental fate, bioaccumulation, ecotoxicity, metabolism, and toxicity). It enables the identification of chemicals of high concern even with no available testing data. In particular, the database includes predictions for 600,000 chemicals and more from over 200 (Q)SAR models. When possible, the endpoints have been modeled in the three software systems Leadscope, CASE Ultra and SciQSAR. The published predictions are abbreviated predictions (simple yes/no) and do not include detailed information about specific alerts identified. Moreover, the database is linked with the OECD QSAR toolbox. It is a valuable tool that enables the screening and assessment of hazardous substances, contributing to the elimination of animal testing (DTU Food, 2018).
- **EPI Suite:** The Estimation Programs Interface -EPI Suite™ v4.11 is a Windows-based suite developed by the US EPA that provides free programs of physical/chemical property and environmental fate estimations for exposure assessment. EPI Suite™ employs several QSPR (quantitative structure-property relationships) models for predicting the environmental properties of chemicals, using structural fragment counts and correction factors as molecular descriptors. It also uses two QSAR models for estimating water solubility, WSKOW and WATERNT respectively (EPA, 2023a).
- **GreenScreen:** GreenScreen for Safer Chemicals is a process for evaluating chemical hazards and distinguishing harmful substances while also identifying safer substitutes. It provides a standardized and simple score to improve communication throughout supply chains and companies. Each chemical examined by GreenScreen is assigned a Benchmark number, with higher Benchmark numbers signifying increasingly safer substances (CPA, 2018). GreenScreen is largely used to analyze and compare specific chemicals; it does not, however, review or compare products, processes, or alternative technologies (SUBSPORTplus, 2019a).
- **GHS Column Model:** GHS Column Model is a tool for safety assessment and substitution of hazardous substances. Substances, such as chemicals and materials or mixtures can be compared using the tool based on six hazard endpoints. The user decides on the best option after comparing endpoints both individually and collectively. In general, GHS Column Model is not used for thorough process change assessments (OECD, 2022). The risk assessment criteria are based on H phrases, the physical form of the substance, vapour pressure, the German classification of aquatic hazards, and the process type. The risk levels range from negligible to extremely high. The substitute with the lowest hazard level will be preferred. The model is applicable to limited one-time substitutions of products or chemicals. Lastly, this method is aimed at both SMEs and non-technical users (SUBSPORTplus, 2019b).
- **OECD SAAToolbox:** The OECD Substitution and Alternatives Toolbox (SAAToolbox) is a collection of resources to assist in assessing chemical hazards and determining possible alternatives. In general, SAAToolbox is a repository, in which case studies regarding safer by design are included, as well as alternatives and non-hazard assessment tools.

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- **OECD QSAR Toolbox:** The OECD QSAR Toolbox is a freely available software designed to aid in chemical hazard assessment owned by both ECHA and OECD. The tool allows the identification of structural alerts for different endpoints, provides structurally similar chemicals or chemicals with the same mode of action, and contains existing experimental data. It contributes to the application of non-animal assessment methods and reduces the need for unnecessary animal testing, all while protecting human health and the environment. The toolbox includes 902 (Q)SAR models used to predict different properties. The QSAR models are distinguished into four categories; QSARs predicting physical-chemical properties, environmental fate and transport, ecotoxicological information, and human health hazards. (QSAR Toolbox, 2022).
- **OncoLogic:** OncoLogic™ is an expert system that evaluates the carcinogenic potential of chemicals using structure-activity relationship (SAR) analysis rules, developed by the US EPA. The updated version 9.0 has been released in 2021 in collaboration with the OECD. It is a tool designed to provide guidance and information on the identification of chemical hazards associated with cancer, as well as the intrinsic hazards of a new chemical. OncoLogic enables the safety assessment of both new (early in the design) and existing chemicals, and it can also be applied to the process safety approach by assessing chemical by-products with carcinogenic potential. Moreover, it can evaluate the carcinogenicity of four subsystems of substances: 1) fibers, 2) polymers, 3) metals, metalloids, and metal containing compounds (version 8.0), and 4) organic chemicals (version 9.0) (EPA, 2019, EPA, 2023b).
- **Subselect:** The SubSelect IT guide was developed on behalf of UBA. It is a guide to selecting sustainable chemicals. It assists you in gathering information on hazard, resources and CO₂ emissions to carefully consider substitution requirements or identify alternative substances. Furthermore, it guides the user in selecting more sustainable chemicals and is applicable for chemical substitution (Umweltbundesamt, 2020).
- **SUBSPORTplus:** The SUBSPORTplus is generated from the SUBSPORT project. This portal provides information to assist in substituting substances and finding safer alternatives. It consists of different sections describing the process of substitution, containing the respective regulations, and including cases of substitution (SUBSPORTplus, 2019c).
- **ToxTree:** ToxTree is a hazard assessment tool that uses QSARs for estimating toxic hazard chemical properties. It is integrated into an open-source application for risk and hazard assessment of compounds, developed by Ideacon Ltd. and EC-JRC. It utilizes the physicochemical and structural properties of compounds and uses a decision tree approach for Cramer classification (I, II, or III, from potentially least to most toxic). Additionally, it is implemented for the Verhaar scheme for aquatic modes of action, for skin and eye irritation and corrosion, for mutagenicity and carcinogenicity (Benigni-Bossa rule-base), and other predictions such as protein and DNA binding alerts (TOXIT, 2022, Labcorp, 2023).
- **VEGA:** VEGA is a freely available software, developed by Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri (IRFMN), which provides tens of Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) models for predicting physico-chemical and (eco)toxicological properties of chemical substances. The QSAR models in VEGA are based on other tools, including EPI Suite, Toxtree, CAESAR, and SARpy. VEGA combines the QSAR models with read-across tools for the evaluation of the results. The QSAR models are built on three fundamental components, which are the property under investigation, the chemical data and the algorithm connecting the two. For the prediction evaluation, parameters for each of these components have been developed, which are then combined into a value known as the applicability domain index (ADI) of the model. In addition to aiding the user through the assessment, this index can

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also boost the reliability of the evaluation. VEGA evaluates the similarity of the respective compounds by using a similarity score from 1 to 0. All of the resulting predictions and data are organized in a summary report created by VEGA for the users (VEGA HUB, 2016).

- ZZS Similarity tool:** The ZZS similarity enables screening and prioritisation (for further assessment) of substances by risk assessors, academia and industrial partners, on the basis of the molecular/structural similarity of the assessed substances to known substances previously classified in the Netherlands as ‘substances of very high concern’ (SVHC, or ‘ZZS’ in Dutch) (Wassenaar et al., 2022). It was developed by the RIVM and funded by the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management. The underlying principle is that high resemblance in the chemical structure of a substance can be an indication of comparable properties and effects (Wassenaar et al., 2022, Johnson and Maggiora, 1990). A list of known Substances of Very High Concern is considered as the main benchmark for the similarity tool with the goal to rapidly screen and subsequently regulate novel chemicals of potential high concern, therefore aiding in the overall workload of evaluation of novel chemicals. Using basic input (SMILES-code or CAS-number) the ZZS similarity models work by generating the chemical fingerprint of the substance to derive a similarity coefficient (Todeschini et al., 2012, Wassenaar et al., 2022, Willett, 2014).

Table 4. Tools for Hazard Assessment

Tool	Description	Type of tool (method, model, software, etc.)	Link
AMBIT tool	An open-source chemoinformatic tool developed by Cefic-LRI to aid businesses in the assessment of chemical safety.	Software	URL°
ChemCoach	A tool that guides companies to integrate the chemical safety of their products	Method	URL°
ChemForward SAFER	A tool that assists individual suppliers in identifying safer ingredients to ensure human and environmental safety	Method	URL°
Danish (Q)SAR Database	The Danish (Q)SAR database is a free searchable online repository of structural information and (Q)SAR predictions for more than 650,000 discrete organic substances	Software	URL°
EPI Suite™	A Windows-based suite that provides free programs of physical/chemical property and environmental fate estimations for exposure assessment.	Software	URL°
GHS Column Model	A tool for safety assessment and substitution of hazardous substances.	Method	URL°
GreenScreen for Safer Chemicals	A method for assessing chemical hazards and identifying hazardous chemicals as well as safer substitutes.	Method	URL°
OECD SAAToolbox	A collection of resources to assist in assessing chemical hazards and determining possible alternatives.	Toolbox	URL°
OECD QSAR Toolbox	A software designed to aid in chemical hazard assessment and increase mechanistic and other knowledge about chemical substances cost-effectively.	Software	URL°
Oncologic	An Expert System to Evaluate the Carcinogenic Potential of Chemicals	Software	URL°

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Tool	Description	Type of tool (method, model, software, etc.)	Link
SubSelect	A guide to select sustainable chemicals by gathering information on hazard, resources and CO ₂ emissions and identifying alternatives.	Software	URL°
SUBSPORTplus	A portal that provides information to assist in substituting substances and finding safer alternatives.	Database	URL°
Toxtree	Toxic Hazard Estimation by decision tree approach	Software	URL°
VEGA	VEGA provides tens of QSAR models to predict toxicity, ecotoxicity, environmental, and physicochemical properties of chemical substances	Software	URL°
ZZS Similarity tool	A tool for screening and prioritization of substances based on the molecular/structural similarity of the assessed substances to known substances	Model	URL°

Table 5. QSAR models and their application used for the characterization of P, B, M, T and S properties (van Dijk et al., 2022).

Criteria	Endpoint	QSAR model	Application of QSAR: Filter or Ranking (with desired value or range)
P	Ready biodegradability	EPISUITE: BIOWIN 3 and BIOWIN 5	Pre-selection filter
	Aerobic biodegradability	EPISUITE: BIOWIN 3 and BIOWIN 6 (average)	Ranking (desired value as high as possible)
	Anaerobic biodegradability	EPISUITE: BIOWIN 7	Ranking (desired value as high as possible)
B	BCF	EPISUITE: BCFBAF	All structures predicted non-concerning
	LogKow	EPISUITE: KOWWIN	Range between 1 and 3 [1].
M	LogKoc	EPISUITE: KOCWIN and VEGA: OPERA KOC (average)	Ranking (undesired below 1, soft lower cutoff between 1 and 2. Desired value between 2 and 4 [2])
T	Non-Mutagenicity	VEGA: consensus model	Pre-selection filter and ranking of reliability (desired value as high as possible)
	EDC properties: Estrogen, Androgen, Thyroid alpha and beta receptor effects	VEGA: Estrogen (IRFMN/CERAPP), Androgen (IRFMN/COMPARA), Thyroid alpha/beta (NRMEA)	Pre-selection filter with qualitative outputs
S	Synthesizability based on chemical symmetry (SynSymPoints)	None, score created using rdkit and SMARTS substructure matching	Ranking (desired value as high as possible)

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Criteria	Endpoint	QSAR model	Application of QSAR: Filter or Ranking (with desired value or range)
	Exclusion of small rings (SynRingPoints)	None, score created using rdkit and SMARTS substructure matching	Ranking (negative value for rings, desired value as high as possible)

2.4.1.3 Tools for Risk Assessment

This section includes a list of risk assessment tools:

- **Chesar:** Chesar v3.7.3 (Chemical Safety Assessment and Reporting) was developed by ECHA and is used for exposure assessment and risk characterizations, supporting companies in their Chemical Safety Assessments by generating a Chemical Safety Report (CSR). It is an integrated tool of three generic exposure assessment models; ECETOC TRA for occupational and consumer exposure and the EUSES fate model. The tool can be used for both qualitative and quantitative risk assessment, with the former relying on predicted no-effect levels and the latter on ECETOC TRA and EUSES models. To start the assessment process for a certain substance with Chesar, the hazard assessment according to Annex I of REACH must be available. In particular, EUSES and ECETOC-TRA are built-in Chesar and estimate the environmental exposure concentrations and the workers' and consumers' concentrations respectively (ECHA, 2021).
- **EUSES:** EUSES 2.2.0 (European Union System for the Evaluation of Substances) is an environmental risk assessment tool for new and existing chemicals and biocides, developed by the European Commission and RIVM and is hosted by ECHA. It is a tier 2 screening model and evaluates all phases of the substance's life cycle throughout its environmental fate (Lijzen and Rikken, 2004). The exposure assessment is carried out with the use of exposure scenarios and their acceptable worst-case scenarios, whilst the fate and dispersion of a substance in a sewage treatment plant are evaluated using the SimpleTreat model 4.0. Moreover, ConsExpo can be started from EUSES (consumer exposure assessment) and the output of ConsExpo can be exported to and used in EUSES. (Sub)chronic worker exposure is estimated using the EASE model, while values of acute exposure can be entered by the user. EUSES also employs QSAR models for estimating the fate parameters (e.g., partition coefficient, bioconcentration factors) (ECHA, 2019).
- **INTEGRA:** The objective of INTEGRA is to bring together all available information within a coherent methodological framework for assessing the source-to-dose continuum for the entire life cycle of substances covering an extensive chemical space. Hence, the major component of INTEGRA is a unified computational platform that integrates environmental fate, exposure, and internal dose dynamically in time. In this way, the platform is able to differentiate between biomonitoring data corresponding to steady exposure patterns as opposed to acute, one-off exposures. The INTEGRA platform includes: a multimedia model to account for multi-scale (far-field exposure) interactions affecting the environmental transport and fate of chemicals, a generic PBTK model that captures satisfactorily life stage changes and physiological and metabolic efficiency change over an individual's lifetime (from conception till 80 years of age), an indoor micro-environmental modelling and detailed personal exposure assessment (near field exposure), and an inverse modelling module for exposure reconstruction and human biomonitoring (HBM) data assimilation (Sarigiannis et al., 2016).

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- **RAST and CHEF:** RAST (Risk Analysis Screening Tool) serves as a screening tool designed to facilitate companies in identifying process risks through a combination of Hazards Identification and Risk Assessment (HIRA). Moreover, RAST also possesses the capability to perform ‘Layer of Protection Analysis’ (LOPA) (CCPS, 2021) and also, utilizes Chemical Hazard Engineering Fundamental (CHEF). CHEF covers the characterization of chemical properties such as flammability, toxicity and reactivity. Additionally, it incorporates models for estimating human hazards including toxic and flammable releases and provides methods for the quantification of risk (Safety Delta Netherlands, 2021).
- **RISKOFDERM:** RISKOFDERM is a simple-to-use toolkit for the assessment and management of health risks from occupational dermal exposure. The toolkit was created after an investigation into the factors that cause dermal hazards and exposure and the results were organized into a decision tree. It translates the information given by the user into broad data categories of hazard and exposure that lead to a rough estimate of health risk from dermal exposure. By using this toolkit, users can assess whether the chemical is harmful to dermal or systemic health. Data is entered by the user and organized into hazard categories. After following the decision-tree evaluation, users are recommended to take action to mitigate the risk (Subash, 2022).
- **RSEI model:** The Risk-Screening Environmental Indicators (RSEI) is a multi-media model for exploring toxic substance releases from industrial and federal facilities. The model can monitor changes in potential long-term human health impacts over time. It is a screening-level tool that employs worst-case scenarios regarding toxicity and potential exposure (EPA, 2022c). It estimates the risk of human exposure as a result of consuming contaminated fish or drinking contaminated water. Moreover, it calculates the dose, or how much the chemical could enter a human’s body, based on the calculated air and water concentration, as well as the different ingestion and inhalation toxicity weights. In the RSEI, a score is computed by multiplying the chemical’s toxicity weight by its estimated dose and the total human exposures (EPA, 2022c). Based on the EPA’s Toxic Release Inventory (TRI), chemical releases and transfers are modeled by the RSEI to determine their chronic human health effects. As a result, each release type is calculated based on the reported amounts of these releases. The model focuses only on the effects on general populations (EPA, 2013). Users can access RSEI results by using the EasyRSEI dashboard.
- **Stoffenmanager:** Stoffenmanager is a knowledge-based platform designed to reduce workplace exposure risks to hazardous substances and biological agents. It classifies a product’s hazards using the H-phrases. A source-receptor model developed by Cherrie and Schneider (1999) and Marquart et al (2008) underpins the exposure algorithm and includes source emission and contaminant dispersion-related modifying variables. Exposure calculation is based on the type of handling, inherent product characteristics, local controls and overall air conditioning (Marquart et al., 2008). Additionally, the model for estimating skin exposure is based on the RISKOFDERM Toolkit (Stoffenmanager, 2022). It also includes several modules, such as Control Banding, Quantitative Exposure Assessment, REACH Worker Exposure, and a nano module. Lastly, the model ranks exposure situations based on process information, physicochemical properties, and mass balances (Tielemans et al., 2008a).

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Table 6: Tools for Risk Assessment

Tool	Description	Type of tool (method, model, software, etc.)	Link
Chesar	A tool to assist REACH registrants. It uses a workflow to perform exposure assessments and risk characterisations, enabling it to generate a Chemical Safety Report (CSR) and communicate exposure scenarios (ES).	Software	URL°
EUSES	A software that assists in the quantitative assessment of the environmental risks related to chemical substances.	Software	URL°
INTEGRA	A coherent methodological framework for assessing the source-to-dose continuum for the entire life cycle of substances covering an extensive chemical space	Model	URL°
RAST and CHEF	A screening tool, that identifies the process risks and assists with hazard assessment, scenario development and risk analysis by using the CHEF documentation.	Software	URL°
RISKOFLDERM	A toolkit designed to aid in the assessment and management of workplace hazards and chemical exposure.	Toolkit	URL°
RSEI model	A multi-media model for exploring toxic substance releases from industrial and federal facilities.	Model	URL°
Stoffenmanager	An occupational exposure and hazard identification tool, which is based on process information, physicochemical properties, and mass balances	Software	URL°

2.4.2 Tools for Sustainability Assessment

- **Brightway2:** Brightway2 is a widely used open-source LCA software that enables users to analyze the environmental impacts of products and processes. It offers a comprehensive toolkit for conducting life cycle assessments, including database management, impact assessment methods, and uncertainty analysis. Brightway2's user-friendly interface and extensive functionality make it a valuable tool for sustainability professionals and researchers seeking to make informed decisions about their environmental footprint.
- **Circulytics:** Circulytics is a tool that assists companies in measuring the circularity of their business. More specifically, it is a decision-support tool that can measure the circularity performance of a company and provide transparency, including an extensive list of indicators. The circularity measure is distinguished into the enablers and the outcomes categories of indicators. The former consists of indicators identifying the circularity potential of the company, while the latter includes indicators that measure materials and water flows, energy use, product design, etc. These indicators are evaluated using a score for the two categories respectively to interpret the measure of the company's circularity performance (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2022).
- **CML Method:** The CML method is a midpoint LCIA method using several impact categories, such as eutrophication, climate change, and human toxicity. It groups the impact categories into two groups: Obligatory and additional impact categories and contains more than 1700 flows. Obligatory impact categories (baseline) are used widely in LCA studies and additional impact categories are depended on the requirements of each study (non-baseline) (Menoufi, 2011), (Acero et al., 2016).

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- **ECON:** ECON is a software that deals with cost calculations and economic analysis of a process utilizing published cost models. ECON has its own database of cost parameters, which can be changed by the user. This software consists of 3 parts: Input, output data parts and analysis part. In the input data part, the user chooses continuous or batch procedure, Raw materials and Products and Equipment and Utilities. In output data capital Investment, operation cost, total product cost and economic analysis are analyzed. Lastly, pie charts, sensitivity analysis and alternative cases are proposed (PSEforSPEED, 2021b).
- **Environmental Footprint (EF) Method:** The Environmental Footprint (EF) v3.1 method is a Life Cycle Impact Assessment method recommended by the European Commission to assess the environmental impacts of products and organizations throughout their lifecycle. EF v3.1 method includes the following 16 midpoint impact categories: 1) Climate change, 2) Ozone depletion, 3) Human toxicity, cancer, 4) Human toxicity, non-cancer, 5) Particulate matter, 6) Ionising radiation, human health, 7) Photochemical Ozone formation, human health, 8) Acidification, 9) Eutrophication, terrestrial, 10) Eutrophication, freshwater, 11) Eutrophication, marine, 12) Ecotoxicity, freshwater, 13) Land use, 14) Water use, 15) Resource use, minerals and metals, 16) Resource use, fossil. The impact categories are based on models that connect the inventory phase (Life Cycle Inventory) to the impact assessment phase, and each one has a representative indicator. Moreover, a characterization factor is computed for each of the impact categories. Next, the LCIA results are divided by normalization factors and then the normalized results are multiplied by a set of weighting factors indicating the importance of each impact category (EC, 2022).
- **Fast Track LCA:** Fast Track Life Cycle Assessment is a form of LCA where time-consuming aspects of conventional LCA are predetermined and where required data can be accessed rapidly. It is meant to benefit a type of user that is faced with large multi-substance, multi-material, or multi-component product systems, or the type of user who aspires to perform rapid assessments at early design stages. As per the definition by Prof. Dr.ir. J. Vogtlander (TU Delft), fast-track LCA is a type of LCA approach where the output of the calculations of the classical (i.e. full scale) LCA is input for the Fast Track calculation, and where the methodological focus is not on compiling the life cycle inventory and performing a full life cycle impact assessment, but on the comparison of design alternatives. In practice, Fast Track LCA is more accessible because a user needs only to multiply the inputs and outputs of the (user-defined) process of interest with the corresponding single impact indicator in an associated database.
- **GaBi:** GaBi is an LCA software developed by Thinkstep, that provides a product sustainability solution and can be used to support a Life Cycle Assessment, Life Cycle Costing, Life Cycle Reporting and a Life Cycle Working Environment. It is a useful tool for businesses, enabling them to decide effectively about a product's production and life cycle. It is a modeling and reporting software, that takes into account the life cycle of every element of a product or process, while it can also assess socioeconomic data (GaBi, 2022). GaBi provides a database supplied by Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) data from industry, academia and organizations. This database contains all of the relevant information about a product (PE INTERNATIONAL AG, 2012).
- **GLAM:** Global Life Cycle Impact Assessment method (GLAM) provides endpoint characterization results for various impact categories, developed as a global consensus-based method under the auspices of the Life Cycle Initiative hosted at the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP).

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- Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of products and organization:** The Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations were developed as part of the UNEP/SETAC Initiative to aid practitioners in evaluating the social and socioeconomic impacts of products, their value chains, and organizations over their lifecycle. These Guidelines address the four stages of a Social Life Cycle Assessment, which are i) the goal and scope definition, ii) the determination of the inventory, iii) the social impact assessment, and iv) the interpretation of the results. Furthermore, the document provides guidance on the application of the Social Organization Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA), focusing on the impacts of an organization's life cycle. This framework is an invaluable resource and guide for anyone planning to implement S-LCA (UNEP, 2020).
- Higg Platform:** Higg is a platform used by businesses to assess the impact of their products and improve their sustainability by altering their environmental and social footprints and improving emissions, water usage, and working conditions, among other things. Its strategy considers the carbon, water, waste, energy, social, and labor implications. It assesses the full life cycle of products from manufacturing to transportation and retail. It includes assessment methodologies, such as the **Sustainable Apparel Coalition's Higg Index** and the **Apparel Impact Institute's Carbon Leadership Program** (Higg, 2022a). Higg MSI provides a dataset of material impacts, in order to understand the costs, benefits, and tradeoffs of different materials (Higg, 2022b).
- ICAS:** ICAS (Tools Integrated in one Computer-Aided System) provides a collection of tools developed to solve various problems. Some of the tools are relevant to process-product modeling, synthesis & design, property modelling, Databases and numerical tools, etc. It provides algorithms, methods and models for efficient problem solving (PSEforSPEED, 2021c).
- IMPACT World+:** IMPACT World+ is a globally regionalized Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) method developed as an update of previous LCIA methods; IMPACT 2002+, LUCAS, and EDIP. It is based on a midpoint-damage framework consisting of four different complementary viewpoints for the presentation of the LCIA profile, which are the impacts at the midpoint level, the impacts at the damage level, the impacts at the damage level on the area of protection (AoP) and the impacts at the damage level on the area of concern (AoC). Impact World+ considers both midpoint (18 indicators) and endpoint impact categories (21 indicators), which are separated into short-term and long-term damage. With IMPACT World+, the emissions and energy consumption from all over the world can be assessed. This is accomplished by employing characterization factors at four hierarchical resolution levels: global, continental, country, and native based on all regional impact indicators and the related uncertainty of spatial variability (Bulle et al., 2019).
- LC-Impact:** LC-Impact is a regionalized Life Cycle Impact Assessment methodology developed within the EU-FP7 project. The primary goal of LC-Impact is to create a "living" LCIA technique that is regularly updated and incorporates all new advancements in LCIA. It is focused on the three main areas of protection in LCIA studies; human health, ecosystem quality (terrestrial, freshwater, and marine ecosystems), and natural resources estimating characterization factors for 11 endpoint impact categories. Specifically, LC-Impact quantifies human health damage in disability adjusted life years (DALY), ecosystem quality damage in global PDF (*potentially disappeared fraction of species over time*), and mineral resources damage in additional ore extracted (kg). Finally, LC-Impact features spatial detailed characterization factors for almost all the impact categories, with the exception of climate change, ionizing radiation, and stratospheric ozone depletion (Verones et al., 2020). Comparatively to

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other LCIA methods, LC-IMPACT puts regional species losses into perspective by putting global species loss in perspective.

- **LCSoft:** LCSoft performs LCA of products and does calculations for chemical and biochemical processes and measures its environmental footprint (carbon, water and ecological footprint). Also, the part analysis of LCSoft, includes contribution analysis, sensitivity analysis and process alternative comparison. LCSoft is integrated with other process design tools such as process simulation, economic analysis (ECON), and sustainability index calculation (SustainPro) (PSEforSPEED, 2021d).
- **openLCA:** OpenLCA is an open-source software tool that is widely used for conducting LCA and sustainability analyses of products, services, and processes. It provides a user-friendly interface for conducting LCAs, and it is widely used in academia and industry for environmental sustainability assessments. It also supports a wide range of impact assessment methodologies, making it a flexible and powerful tool for conducting environmental sustainability assessments. This software provides a comprehensive platform for data management, impact assessment, and reporting for life cycle assessments. OpenLCA provides a comprehensive platform for conducting LCAs and supports a wide range of impact assessment methodologies, including the ISO standards and Eco-indicator.
- **Portfolio Sustainability Assessment (PSA):** Portfolio Sustainability Assessment (PSA) is a methodology for enhancing the sustainability performance of a product portfolio. Its primary goal is to assist businesses in the development and implementation of new PSA methodologies. PSA can be applied for existing products and services as well as R&D projects. In this context, the Chemical Industry Methodology for PSA developed a digitalization tool, known as WBCSD PSA — Digitalization tool to start, to support the PSA methodology and better interpret its results. This tool is a guidance tool in an MS Excel worksheet form, consisting of 5 steps for assessing the environmental and social performance of a product throughout its lifecycle (WBCSD, 2021, WBCSD, 2018).
- **ProCAFD:** ProCAFD (part of ICAS toolbox) is a software for sustainable process design, which has a workflow with three stages; synthesis stage, design and analysis stage and innovation stage. At the synthesis stage, problem definition and analysis steps are incorporated. Also, in the second stage, steps connected to process design and ECON, LCsoft, sustainability & safety analysis are contained. The third stage focuses on process optimization and intensification (PSEforSPEED, 2021a).
- **ProCAPD:** ProCAPD (Computer-Aided Tool Chemical Product Design) is a software for chemical product design & analysis. It includes stages of problem definition, design-analysis stage, and verification stage. Also, allows access to vast amounts of data that could be useful for chemical substitution (PSEforSPEED, 2021b).
- **ProScale:** ProScale was developed as a method for a hazard and exposure-based quantitative scoring system for comparing direct chemical risks (corresponding to near-field human toxicity) to workers, professionals, and consumers associated with products in a life cycle perspective (Rydberg et al 2017). The method aims to: (i) assess the relevant direct exposure potential along the whole life cycle; (ii) use existing data, when available, e.g. REACH based; (iii) allow comparison in relation to technical performance; and (iv) be relevant for business-to-business and business-to-customer communication. ProScale estimates a score for a specific instance of exposure for a given unit process combined with the corresponding hazard for the substance considered. The score is then related to the amount of the process necessary for the fulfillment of the functional unit as defined by the product system. This is done for all relevant exposure instances so that eventually ProScale scores for all included exposure instances make up the ProScale assessment score at the required level of aggregation.

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- **ReCiPe:** The ReCiPe methodology is developed by many LCA developers, such as RIVM, CML, PRé Consultants, et al. ReCiPe is based on CML 2002 and EI99 (Eco-Indicator 99) methodologies and the indicator scores are determined in a similar way as in the EI99 method. It combines the modeling of eighteen impact midpoint and three endpoint approaches. It estimates the damages at the end of the cause-effect chain by correlating the impact categories and their damage pathways (Menoufi, 2011).
- **SimaPro:** SimaPro serves as LCA software, aiding businesses in comprehending the environmental impact of their products and identifying alternative options that align with sustainability goals. It supports the environmental impact assessment of products or processes across several impact categories (i.e. climate change, eutrophication, resource scarcity, human toxicity) taking into account their whole life cycle. Additionally, SimaPro includes a list of databases, such as Ecoinvent and GABI Database, to provide data for environmental performance estimates. Lastly, SimaPro offers the inclusion of normalization and weighting factors, enriching the depth and precision of the results obtained from the life cycle assessment (Mark Goedkoop et al., 2016).
- **SUPER-O:** Super-O deals with processing routes, which are needed to convert selected raw materials to desired products. Processing routes are represented in terms of steps, and intervals, which are the available alternatives at each step and the connections between the intervals of different steps. The user describes the superstructure and provides the required input data. The Super-O mathematical programming model, MILP or MINLP, is solved through numerical internal or external solvers. (PSEforSPEED, 2021j).
- **SUSTAINPRO:** SustainPro is an EXCEL-based software that performs sustainable process design and provides options for retrofit and process performance analysis. It requires mass and energy balance data, which are obtained from the plant or process simulations. It also requires various cost-related data to perform the retrofit analysis (the prices for utilities, the prices for chemicals, etc.). The user chooses the steps of the workflow (solution steps) at SustainPro's interface and as outputs, suggestions for improving the process are given, along with calculated values of the sustainability metrics and safety indices (PSEforSPEED, 2021c).
- **Sustainability method selection tool:** The Sustainability method selection tool is a tool that assists users in selecting the proper method for their sustainability assessment in three steps. It helps users choose between a wide range of methods for measuring sustainability, which may cover a variety of scopes and timescales, to address a sustainability-oriented problem definition. Moreover, through the "Substance Search," it can check whether a chemical substance is currently listed as harmful to humans and/or the environment, based on several national and international regulations (RIVM, 2022b).
- **Umberto LCA:** Umberto LCA is an LCA software tool that aids in analyzing the environmental impact of a product or process throughout its whole life cycle. Umberto supports the creation of comprehensive life cycle inventories (LCI), enabling the users to obtain a thorough understanding of their assessment, taking into consideration numerous impact categories such as resource depletion, energy use, and climate change. Another feature that Umberto provides is scenario analysis, where the users can model and assess different scenarios of environmental performance (iPoint, 2022).
- **USEtox:** USEtox is the UNEP/SETAC global scientific consensus model developed under the auspices of and formally endorsed by the Life Cycle Initiative hosted at the United Nations Environment Programme for characterizing human toxicity and ecotoxicity impacts (Westh et al., 2015, Hauschild et al., 2008). USEtox is an integrated near-field/far-field multimedia fate, multi-pathway exposure and (eco-) toxicity effect modeling framework for characterizing toxicity and ecotoxicity of chemical life cycle

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emissions and chemicals in products for use in Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), chemical substitution, and consumer and population exposure and risk prioritization. USEtox provides midpoint and endpoint characterization factors, and screening-level risk results (Rosenbaum et al., 2008, Fantke et al., 2021). The model is applicable to the consumer and indoor environment, the urban scale, the continental scale, and the global scale. USEtox's main result is a set of characterization factors. Exposure, fate, and effect parameters for human toxicity and ecotoxicity are included in the model and are combined to generate the human toxicity and ecotoxicity characterization factors. Human cancer, reproduction/developmental toxicity and other non-cancer toxicity, as well as freshwater aquatic toxicity, are addressed as indicators in the model.

Table 7: Tools for Sustainability Assessment

Tool	Description	Type of tool (method, model, software, etc.)	Link
Brightway2	Software for advanced LCA calculations	Software	URL°
Circulytics	A tool that supports companies in measuring their circularity	Method	URL°
CML Method	An LCA method for estimating the environmental impact of a product using several impact categories.	Method	URL°
ECON	A software for economic analysis of processes.	Software	URL°
EF- Method	A Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) method that estimates the environmental footprint	Method	URL°
Fast Track LCA	A form of LCA where time-consuming aspects of conventional LCA are predetermined and where required data can be accessed rapidly	Method	URL°
GaBi	An LCA software that provides a product sustainability solution and can be used to support a Life Cycle Assessment, a Life Cycle Costing, a Life Cycle Reporting and a Life Cycle Working Environment.	Software	URL°
GLAM	Global Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) method providing endpoint characterization results for various impact categories, developed as global consensus-based method under the auspices of the Life Cycle Initiative hosted at the United Nations Environment Programme	Method	URL°
Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of products and organizations	A guidance to assist stakeholders in assessing the social and socio-economic impacts of products' life cycles, their related value chains and organizations	Methodology	URL°
Higg Platform	A platform, which is utilized by companies to identify the impact of their products and enhance their sustainability.	Platform	URL°
ICAS	A toolbox relevant to process-product modeling, synthesis & design, property modelling and including Databases and numerical tools	Software	URL°
IMPACT World+	Global spatially-differentiated Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) method providing endpoint characterization results within a consistent LCIA framework	Method	URL°
LC-Impact	Global regionalized Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) method combining endpoint characterization	Method	URL°

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Tool	Description	Type of tool (method, model, software, etc.)	Link
	results with damages on water and carbon areas of concern within a consistent LCIA framework		
LCSOFT	An LCA software for calculations of environmental footprint	Software	URL°
openLCA	An open-source software for modeling life cycle systems and estimating environmental and socioeconomic indicators.	Software	URL°
Portfolio Sustainability Assessment (PSA)	A methodology for enhancing the sustainability performance of a product portfolio	Methodology	URL°
ProCAFD	A software for sustainable process design.	Software	URL°
ProCAPD	A software for chemical product design & analysis.	Software	URL°
ProScale	A method that compares chemical risks associated with products throughout their life cycle using a scoring system based on hazard and exposure.	Method	URL°
ReCiPe	A Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) method addresses several environmental concerns and estimates the damage at the end of the cause-effect chain.	Method	URL°
SimaPro	An LCA software that helps companies understand the environmental footprint of their products and find more sustainable substitutes.	Software	URL°
SUPER-O	A process design software for the transformation of raw materials into products	Software	URL°
Sustainability method selection tool	A tool that assists users in selecting the proper method for their sustainability assessment.	Methodology	URL°
SUSTAINPRO	A software that performs sustainable process design and provides options for retrofit and process performance analysis.	Software	URL°
Umberto LCA	An LCA software, that is addressed to industries and for research & education and it measures the environmental footprint of products.	Software	URL°
USEtox	A multimedia fate, exposure and effect framework for characterizing toxicity and ecotoxicity of chemical life cycle emissions and chemicals in products for use in Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), chemical substitution, consumer and population exposure and risk prioritization, providing midpoint and endpoint characterization factors, and screening-level risk results.	Model	URL°

2.5 Gaps identification and recommendations for the PARC SSbD toolbox

Since SSbD is a new concept that is constantly being developed, there aren't yet enough tools available to implement the SSbD framework. As a result of that, there are still gaps in the development and integration of tools, such as models, software, and methods, for safety and sustainability assessment, which is the main goal of the PARC SSbD toolbox. According to the overview, a framework that enables the synthesis of various types of data (e.g., HBM data, epidemiological data and omics data) and the prediction of exposure

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and toxicity of chemicals from the early design phase while minimizing their environmental footprint is needed, even though there are tools that can deliver useful pieces of information. The identification of gaps in existing methodologies and tools can contribute to the development of the conceptual framework of the SSbD toolbox.

The safety assessment workflow requires several aspects and models to facilitate the hazard and exposure assessment. More specifically, exposure and environmental fate models are required for estimating exposure and environmental release and concentration, respectively. Moreover, QSAR models are also valuable tools for the safety assessment of a chemical as they can predict the physicochemical, biological, and environmental fate properties of a compound based on its chemical structure (ECHA, 2022). Additionally, they can evaluate the adverse health effects and exposure levels of hazardous chemical compounds, as well as bioavailability and pharmacokinetic properties (Ruiz et al., 2013). PBPK models also support chemical safety and risk assessment, since they can predict and estimate the internal dose of a chemical in target organs or tissues (Mumtaz et al., 2012). The Systems Biology models are another critical component in the safety assessment workflow for understanding the events that lead to an adverse health outcome and gaining insight into different levels of biological organizations (U.S. EPA, 2014). Subsequently, bioinformatics tools are also of particular importance as they use modern toxicity testing methods (in vitro, omics) and human biomonitoring data for exposure assessment.

These were the criteria for identifying the gaps in the safety assessment tools that were not covered by the previously mentioned overview. In more detail, most of the identified tools focus on exposure (ConsExpo, ART, ECETOC TRA, E-FAST, INTEGRA, Chesar, etc.) and environmental fate models (SimpleBox, E-FAST, EUSES, etc.). A lesser extent of these tools, however, is based on quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) models (AMBIT tool, QSAR Toolbox, VEGA, Danish (Q)SAR Database), while only two of them include PBPK models (Merlin Expo-tool and EPA ExpoBox). It is worth noting that none of the tools include Systems Biology models or Bioinformatics tools. As a result of that, there is a lack of Systems Biology models and Bioinformatics tools to implement the safety assessment approach of the SSbD toolbox. Yet only 7 tools focus on risk assessment via the ingestion route, while 8 are applicable to all exposure routes (inhalation, ingestion, and dermal).

Therefore, some recommendations can be provided on the integration of those tools and the development of new ones within the PARC SSbD toolbox. First of all, there is a need to develop more tools that include QSAR models since they can be used for data gap filling and contribute to the other models required for the safety assessment implementation. They are also important for the estimation of the early biological and adverse health effects of exposure to chemical substances. Furthermore, future tools should place a greater emphasis on PBPK and System Biology models. These models are critical for defining the target dose organ and, as a result, determining the early biological effect. In addition, incorporating bioinformatics tools will assist in the safety assessment of a chemical by providing insights into adverse health outcomes. The development and integration of early-stage tools are also of particular importance.

According to Caldeira et al., (2022b), the sustainability dimension is divided into four particular dimensions; Resources, processing- and product-related aspects, Environmental, Social, and Economic. These dimensions are split into different categories, which are useful to identify the capability of the existing tools to process data from these sections and end up with results. The identification of gaps in the sustainability assessment tools was based on these dimensions. More specifically, most of the tools focus on the categories of the Environmental dimension and the Resources, processing- and product-related aspects (USEtox, ReCiPe, SubSelect, Gabi, openLCA, SimaPro, LC-Impact, IMPACT World+). Some of the most

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covered categories include ‘ecotoxicity and human toxicity’, ‘climate change’, ‘energy’, ‘acidification’, and ‘circularity’. Nevertheless, the categories that are not widely studied in these tools are ‘biodegradability’, ‘aspects that are considered at pressure level’, and ‘other pressure-based indicators’.

On the other hand, the economic dimension is less assessed in comparison with the Environmental and Resources dimensions. However, some sustainability assessment tools deal with economic aspects of products, such as product cost, profitability, and life cycle cost. The main tools which include the above aspects are ECON, Higg platform, SustainPro, ‘Sustainability method selection tool’, and ProCAFD. Nevertheless, ‘market-related criteria’ is a sector that is only included in the Higg platform, ‘Sustainability method selection tool’ and ECON software, and the need for further development exists. Regarding the social dimension, only a few tools are engaged. More specifically, tools, such as the Higg platform, ‘Sustainability method selection’, and ECON study the ‘supply chain responsibility’ aspect. Furthermore, the aspects of customer protection, labor and human rights are underdeveloped, with only the Higg platform and the ‘Sustainability method selection tool’ serving this purpose among the tools examined. The aspects of ‘Human rights’, ‘Customer protection’, ‘Labor rights’, and ‘Market-related criteria’ are the least frequently included but very important aspects of the SSbD framework, so they have to be incorporated. In addition, most of the tools are primarily focused on LCA to assess the sustainability of a chemical/process. Therefore, the use of green chemistry, as well as cheminformatics tools will be essential for eliminating hazards and waste during the manufacturing process of a chemical. As a result, tools for studying and analyzing social and economic aspects have to be integrated into the PARC SSbD toolbox to provide a more comprehensive view. Finally, to enhance the context of the SSbD toolbox, an interface with WP4, WP5, WP6, and WP7 of PARC is crucial.

Figure 7. The percentages of the four sustainability dimensions covered by the tools

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3 SSbD toolbox concept operationalisation

3.1 Translation of the SSbD into SSbD aspects to be addressed during innovation

The SSbD framework has to be integrated to product design process to be effectively implemented. While the toolbox in its final form aims to provide SSbD assessment capabilities along the phases of the stage gate model, at this preliminary stage, it is useful to think about key aspects of safety, sustainability, and functionality should be addressed by the toolbox at early and late stages of the innovation process (Figure 9-11). As the tools are further mapped along the innovation process, these questions will be further refined and expanded.

Figure 8. Safety aspects of chemical to be addressed in early and late phases of innovation

A stage gate step wise breakdown of safety aspects for nanomaterials has been previously described (Dekkers et al., 2020). With additional information on innovative chemical/product development, a more detailed list of safety aspects will be developed.

Figure 9. Sustainability aspects of chemical to be addressed in early and late phases of innovation

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ISO 64 provides a comprehensive overview of sustainability aspects at each life cycle stage, which provides a more comprehensive list to be included in early stage. With additional information on innovative chemical/product development, a more detailed list of sustainability aspects will be developed.

Figure 10. Functionality aspects of chemical to be addressed in early and late phases of innovation

A stage gate step wise breakdown of functionality aspects for nanomaterials has been described (Tavernaro et al., 2021). With additional information on innovative chemical/product development, a more detailed list of functionality aspects will be developed.

With regard to economic and social impact assessment, early and late phase assessments could assess the same impacts, but the later will be quantitative. Due to the preliminary and context specific nature of these methods, these aspects are not provided in this report.

3.2 Input from stakeholders and translation into toolbox requirements

Table 8 provides a first overview of stakeholder needs that are relevant for the further development of the toolbox. Stakeholder needs are categorized as User friendliness, Tool, Data and Workflow. Potential solutions to address these needs via toolbox features and related activities are also proposed, and will be included in the toolbox blueprint. Eliciting stakeholder needs with respect to an ongoing process and additional information will be gathered to further guide toolbox development.

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Table 8. Overview of stakeholder needs

Category	Stakeholder needs	Potential solutions via PARC toolbox and related activities
Ease of Use	Applying the SSbD assessment framework and interpreting the results is complex as it needs in-depth expertise in multiple fields. Smaller companies have limited expertise and resources to apply tools.	Workflow to guide the user Links to related resources (e.g. case studies, guidelines) Use easy to use tools or simplify the user interface Provide trainings on SSbD toolbox use
Tools	Chemical function/Product functionality is an important determinant for substitution considerations or development of a use-case/scenario.	Include tools that assess chemical function/product functionality (e.g. Benefit Assessment Matrix, Quantitative Structure Use Relationships) Develop chemical function/functionality based tools in the toolbox
	Many compounds have multiple functions, and will therefore be used in a large range of possible applications	Develop and include a comprehensive list of chemical functions
	Circularity, Recyclability and Biodegradability are important strategic policy priorities	Include tools and workflows to address these aspects
	The design of a chemical/material/product should also be included in the toolbox.	Include tools and workflows to link assessment to by design actions
	Physio-chemical data are an important key to many chemical and functional aspects	Develop predictive tools / suitable proxies for missing data
	Tools and methods have a scope of applicability to certain groups of chemicals and products	The scope of each tool and the toolbox shall be determined and workflows will guide users to relevant tools or state missing capabilities
Data	Limited data available for assessment and a decision approach on which steps take based on the information.	Include links to databases, Grouping and read across, Develop predictive tools / suitable proxies for missing data
	Data, data-consistency and data-quality is important.	Include/further develop data quality assessment workflows (e.g. Klimisch score for risk assessment, Pedigree matrix for LCA)
	Companies are concerned about the privacy of their data used in the toolbox	Provide the possibility for users to store their own data in desktop (non-cloud) location.
	Chemicals substances as such area enormous group, and the use and the characteristics of use of these chemicals will vary across sectors	Including a sector specific approach to assessment Links to related resources (e.g. case studies for different sectors, sector specific guidelines).
Workflow	Although the framework in its present form is sequential (i.e. require assessment steps to be taken in a specific order), design actions need consideration of trade-offs	Two workflows can be provided: SSbD certification (applies EC SSbD framework at each stage gate), SSbD for design (presents results of assessing hazard, risk, environmental impacts and social and economic impacts simultaneously and links to design actions)

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	If you want to make SSbD-improvements you will want to know where the most benefit will be gained from the product perspective	Two workflows can be provided: chemical based assessment and product based assessment
	In a design/development assessment it may be important to identify where (in which lifecycle stage for example) the best improvement options are to be found.	Provide an aggregation step of risks and impacts within each life cycle stage to assess which stages need most attention
	Signals are needed to address the question if it is worthwhile to continue development.	Include Benefit-Risk based decision support
	The JRC framework provides a scoring system based on the criteria of the SSbD framework.	Incorporate scoring system in SSbD certification workflow
	Not all aspect of the assessment may be relevant at all stages	Provide suitable workflows and guidance on most relevant workflows at each stage of the analysis
	Possibility to assign importance different aspects to enable decision making (e.g. environmental impacts versus chemical safety)	Provide option in workflow to include weights for user preferences
	The use and the characteristics of use of these chemicals will vary across sectors	Including a sector specific approach to assessment Links to related resources (e.g. case studies for different sectors, sector specific guidelines).

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4 PARC SSbD toolbox blueprint

4.1 Key concept of the PARC SSbD toolbox

The PARC SSbD toolbox is envisioned to have capabilities to assess safety, sustainability, functionality as well as social and economic impacts through the innovation process (Figure 11). Each of these modules has tool and data sub-modules that are seamlessly linked following the FAIR principles. The tool modules contain analytical capabilities for assessment at that innovation stage (e.g. hazard, exposure, risk, sustainability, etc). The data module accepts data inputs (e.g. from data, literature), assesses data quality and has predictive in silico tools to estimate missing data (e.g. grouping, read across, QSARs). Both modules are linked to guidance documents and case studies relevant to chemical and product groups being analysed.

Figure 11. SSbD toolbox for early and late innovation process

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4.2 Development of an innovation stage-gate approach

Figure 12. Linking of Safe by Design conceptual framework of PARC with the innovation stage-gate approach

Early innovation stages are characterized by data paucity with regard to the physicochemical, functional, and toxicological properties of a molecule or a material. At the same time, the explorable chemical space at that stage is at its maximal dimensions. Thus, molecular and material modeling and QSARs supported by AI, aka machine learning, techniques are key enabling technologies during this first stage of design. AI will support the SSbD concept in the early stages by generating information and data related to properties and characteristics that might not exist/quantified at that point. Models like QSARs can provide output predictions for the potential toxicity and critical hazards of a chemical, supporting the identification of the most harmful and high-concern substances and determining whether the substances fulfill the SSbD criteria. Furthermore, solutions that qualify for a preliminary assessment stage can benefit from material flow and environmental fate analysis of the chemical/material considered, while still being supported by QSARs and AI as well. It has to be highlighted, however, that the data necessary for the implementation of advanced, data-demanding technologies such as AI and machine learning approaches, need to be FAIR to allow for the seamless integration and coupling of the envisaged computational tools.

Going through the 2nd decision gate, a more detailed description of the chemical/material properties and behavior both in the ecosystem and in humans is possible on the basis of data availability. Models that can estimate environmental releases, as well as multimedia environmental models, can support this stage by offering more comprehensive outputs related to hazard endpoints, due to an increase in available information. SSbD context demands the introduction/integration of numerous data sources from multiple backgrounds. As a result of that, a concrete data investigation and integration plan should be in the SSbD implementation plan. A combination of lab-scale methods and *in silico* tools is warranted for that.

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The substances that go through the 3rd decision gate reach the stage of prototype development. Here, advanced bioinformatics and more integrated testing systems, including multi-omics, NAMs, and effect-based methods, can be linked with phenotypic imaging to produce the necessary experimental evidence regarding early biological effects. Analysis of the experimental data requires the use of the *in silico* tools mentioned above (and already used in earlier innovation stages) to start building the overall safety characterization of the substances that have made it to the 4th decision gate. This will enable a fully described context to be passed in the developing SSbD approach providing all the details needed to portray the safety and the sustainability of a material/chemical/product. In addition to the previous tools, external exposure and physiology-based biokinetic (PBPK) models can be used and the data can be fed into systems biology models assisted yet again by AI for model identification and parameterization. Targeted and high-throughput assays start building the case for identification of early biological effects. As the level of information increases during the innovation stages, these models can provide exposure and risk estimates, as well as aid in the initial risk assessment of substances. At that stage, uncertainty and variability analyses are incorporated to support a robust quantification of ecosystem and human exposure in conjunction with the hazard evaluation.

At the 4th gate, a more comprehensive testing and validation of the performance and of the safety profile of the studied substances is possible. All methods and tools, from high-throughput NAMs and effect-based methods to *in silico* tools mentioned above, would be available to use and the data needed to inform these analyses should be reachable, leading to a concrete background regarding the safety and the sustainability of a chemical. As a result, information obtained from these models and methods can characterize a chemical's safety levels and assist in defining whether it meets the respective SSbD criteria or not. In addition, *in vitro* and a bare minimum of *in vivo* tests would be used on the very few chemical/material candidates that have reached the 5th stage of the innovation continuum. The data derived from this multi-stage and tiered methodological framework would have to be FAIRified and the tools used for the analyses be interoperable.

With regard to sustainability assessment, different methods are employed during early and later innovation stages. Early on (i.e. stages 1 and 2) rule-of-thumb and checklist-based methods comprise rapid circularity assessment (RCA) (Bocken et al., 2016), the GAIA model (Kørnø et al., 2020) or the trade-off navigation framework (TONF) (Kravchenko et al., 2021). On a more advanced (later) innovation stage (i.e. stages 3 to 5) different types of lifecycle assessment (LCA) can be used starting from simplified LCA, to be followed by screening LCA (or business model LCA) up to full LCA and labelling. The application of LCA will be invaluable for decision-making during the later stages of innovation since the environmental impacts of a chemical are defined. This can help in assessing whether the chemical passes the SSbD criteria for each impact category.

Regarding the safe-by-design aspects, the source-to-impacts continuum (Figure 12) is followed to functionally integrate environmental releases, environmental concentrations, multi-pathway and multi-route exposure, internal dose assessment, early biological effects, adverse outcome pathways, risk assessment, and health impact assessment.

In addition, and in bridging to and integrating with social and environmental sustainability through occupational health and process safety considerations, state-of-the-art tools and methodologies for process safety will be employed following the respective industry standards (ISO 45001 and ISO 45003) (Figure 13).

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Regarding environmental sustainability assessment, Lifecycle Assessment (LCA) protocols (ISO 14040, ISO 14044 and the International Reference Lifecycle Data System) will be followed (Figure 14).

Figure 13. Sustainable by design conceptual framework

Several methodological choices need to be made to assess the impacts associated with a certain product or process and to predict system performance on upscaling, especially when prospective LCA is applied based on lab-scale data. The criteria to assess the quality of data and apply cut-off points, the methodology to be used to handle material recycling at the end of lifetime, and the way the environmental burdens and benefits are allocated among the different value chains must be carefully selected, while different methodological options exist for the impact assessment since these methodological choices can drastically influence the results of an LCA. Impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem function and services will also be included in the environmental sustainability assessment. Indicators of genetic and species diversity, functional traits and biophysical structures, and ecological processes will be coined for this alongside a quality pedigree based on data availability and relevance for decision-making towards SSbD implementation for substances such as chemicals and materials.

Absolute sustainability assessment will be addressed by extending the LCA framework to consider planetary boundaries (PB) and introducing the temporal dimension to the assessment and allowing for the determination of the share of safe operating space assigned to each activity in the innovation continuum, thus operationalizing the PB concept for decision making.

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Figure 14. Environmental footprint dimensions

A framework for an environmental footprint family based on nine major biophysical processes and is linked to the planetary boundaries will be explored for use to capture the environmental and ecological footprint of the chemical and material innovation process as shown in Figure 14 (data herein are depicted based on current bibliometric information). The frame matches environmental footprint indicators based on planetary boundaries. The outer red line circles emission footprints, green indicates resource consumption footprints, and black indicates the composite footprint.

4.2.1 Safety components

4.2.1.1 Innovation stage-gate approach of PARC SSbD toolbox

Based on the innovation stage-gate approach, various safety components are employed, as illustrated below.

4.2.1.1.1 Idea

The classification of chemicals as either impacting human health or the environment will be assessed based on QSAR and AI methodologies. Depending on their intended usage, whether in a controlled industrial setting or for consumer products, their potential impact will be estimated through basic simulation techniques.

The principle to pass the first gate 2 demands the generation of green information for a chemical. In brief, the read-across methodologies, QSARs, AI, etc., will provide all these pieces of information in order to characterize if a developing chemical/material/product will be hazardous for human health and the environment. This framework will be strongly supported by the data that the scientific community has already introduced, and that is one of the numerous reasons of FAIR data essentiality in the SSbD context.

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Figure 15. Safety components employed in the idea stage

4.2.1.1.1 QSARs, read across and grouping methods

Quantitative structure–activity relationship (QSAR) models can support the SSbD toolbox by predicting the potential toxicity and environmental impact of substances before they are manufactured and released into the environment, thus they are key component of the sustainability assessment at the early phases of innovation. QSAR models use chemical structure information and data on the biological activity or physicochemical properties of similar chemicals to predict the toxicity or environmental impact of a new chemical. By using QSAR models, modelers and regulators can identify potentially hazardous chemicals and make informed decisions about which chemicals to manufacture and use. This can help to reduce the use of harmful chemicals and promote the development of safer, more sustainable alternatives. Additionally, QSAR models can be used to design chemicals with specific properties that are less toxic and more environmentally friendly. This approach, known as molecular design, can help to reduce the impact of chemicals on human health and the environment while still maintaining the desired functionality.

Grouping and read-across methodologies and tools allowing for the use of existing data for analogues or category members can also assist in this quest. For these to be functional, linkage to databases with valuable information once grouping and read-across approaches are in the toolbox will be required to be set up. At this stage of innovation, QSARs can be used to assess a chemical’s hazard and classify it as hazardous for human health (HH) and the environment (Env) or not, following the SSbD criteria and their indicators. Carcinogenicity, respiratory sensitisation, developmental toxicity and endocrine disruption, as well as aquatic toxicity, persistence, bioaccumulation and toxicity (PBT/vPvB), are some of the major human health and environmental hazards concerns taken into consideration. Tools such as VEGA, EPI Suite, OECD QSAR Toolbox and Danish (Q)SAR Database can provide predictions for human health and environmental hazards as previously mentioned (e.g. carcinogenicity, mutagenicity, aquatic toxicity) that can support decision-making during this stage. Thus, the outputs of these tools can be used to assess whether a substance can pass the SSbD criteria for hazard assessment or not. To conclude, chemoinformatics methods including QSAR models, read across and grouping methods can play an important role in the development of a safe and sustainable by design toolbox facilitating the development of safer alternatives, and ultimately reducing the risk posed by chemical exposure.

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4.2.1.1.2 Detailed investigation - Gate 2

Figure 16. Safety components employed in the stage-gate 2

4.2.1.1.2.1 Releases in the environment

Models for releases in the environment can support the SSbD toolbox by predicting the impact and behavior of chemicals in the environment, and by assessing the potential risks associated with their release. For instance, models can be used to predict the dispersion and transport of chemicals in air, water, and soil, and to estimate their potential impacts on human health and the environment. These models can help to identify areas where chemical releases are likely to have the greatest impact and to inform decisions about where and how chemicals should be used or disposed of. These models can also be used to evaluate the effectiveness of different strategies for managing chemical releases, such as containment, treatment, or remediation. This can help to optimize the use of resources and minimize the impact of chemicals on human health and the environment. Furthermore, models can be used to assess the potential risks associated with the use of chemicals in specific applications, such as consumer products or industrial processes. This can help to identify safer alternatives or design modifications that can reduce the risk of harm. Models such as E-FAST and INTEGRA can be used at this level to generate predictions about the environmental releases and the concentrations (Predicted Environmental Concentrations — PECs) of a chemical under assessment to several environmental compartments. In conclusion, models for releases in the environment can support the SSbD assessment toolbox by providing a tool for predicting the consequences of chemical releases, assessing their potential impacts, and informing decisions about their use and management.

4.2.1.1.2.2 Material flow analysis

Material flow analysis (MFA) is a critical component of SSbD and the PARC SSbD toolbox, subsequently. As described by Brunner and Rechberger (2004), it involves the systematic assessment of material flows and stocks within a space-time-defined system. MFA provides information on material, substances or product flows and stocks within a system by analyzing the inputs and outputs of a process using mass balancing. MFA is an invaluable decision-support tool that can be used in policy areas and the fields of environmental, resource, and waste management, such as material loss and recycling. A material flow analysis begins with the definition of the problem, then moves on to the definition of the system and the selection of substances,

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processes, and system boundaries. The determination of flows and stocks, as well as the identification of uncertainties, are the next steps. Lastly, the analysis results need to be visualized and interpreted (Brunner and Rechberger, 2004). In the context of SSbD, MFA can be used both in the safety and sustainability assessment workflow. MFA, in particular, will be useful as an environmental exposure modelling tool for tracing the flow of a chemical substance through its entire lifecycle and modelling its release into the environment. DPMFA, PMFA, and STAN are tools for material flow analysis proposed to facilitate SSbD at this stage by calculating mass flows through value chains and the respective environmental releases. The outputs of those tools can then be used as inputs for environmental fate models for delivering PECs.

4.2.1.1.2.3 Multimedia environmental modelling

The environmental fate is a key component to properly assess the impact of a substance in the environment. Indeed, this is requested in several regulatory perspectives, for instance, to characterize if a substance is persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT) or very persistent and very toxic (vPvB). This kind of information could also be generated with the use of QSARs, but it will be qualitative. The application of multimedia models will enable the detailed investigation of PBT profiles of chemicals. More recently, the interest has been put also on mobility. This kind of information is highly relevant. If a substance is stable, it will remain in the environment for a long period, and thus all the potentially adverse effects can be generated over a longer period. If a substance is mobile, in the air or water, it will affect a much larger geographical area than a substance that is not mobile.

Beyond models on persistence and air transport, there are models on ready biodegradability, and behaviour within wastewater treatment plants. Furthermore, the models available may be different because they address different categories of substances. Multimedia models, such as INTEGRA and SimpleBox will aid in determining the impact of a chemical on the ecosystems in which it is utilized, as well as how it may affect human exposure, by providing PECs of a chemical (or mixtures thereof) in various environmental compartments (air, water, soil), as well as microenvironments (indoor).

4.2.1.1.3 Prototype development - Gate 3

Figure 17. Safety components employed in the stage-gate 3

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4.2.1.1.3.1 Exposure modelling

Exposure modelling is a crucial component of the SSbD framework. It involves the identification and quantification of potential risks associated with exposure to various substances, such as chemicals or pollutants. This information is then used to inform the design of products, processes, and systems to minimize or eliminate those risks. These modelling components can be integrated into the toolbox in order to evaluate the probable impacts of a substance on human health and the environment or process hypothetical impacts throughout LCA. This includes the raw materials used to create a product, the manufacturing procedure, the use phase, and disposal or recycling. It can also help in the identification of hazards and inform regulators around product and process design, such as selecting safer materials, minimizing emissions, and improving waste management practices. This approach can lead to products that are safer and healthier for both humans and the environment, while also reducing the overall impact of the product. Due to that fact, the incorporation of exposure modelling into the SSbD toolbox seems to be essential and given that, the SSbD toolbox will need a strong background in exposure modelling. In this context, tools such as INTEGRA, EUSES, and ECETOC TRA can be used to provide relevant exposure modelling outputs, such as risk characterization ratios (RCRs) related to environmental, consumer, or worker exposure to the substance under assessment. These results can then be used to evaluate whether a substance (chemical or material) meets the specific SSbD criteria and is thus categorized as safe or not.

Exposure modelling is a capital-intensive procedure that demands comprehensive information until reaches the cumulative description of source to dose pathway (Sarigiannis et al., 2014, Sarigiannis et al., 2016). Such pieces of information are data originating from in vivo and in vitro studies as well as data from available studies. FAIR data necessity is also illustrated here.

Risk characterization for environmental chemicals can now rely on inward dose calculation thanks to the seamless coupling of these modelling components with sophisticated computational techniques for internal dosimetry. Data from high throughput systems, such as those produced by Tox21 project, can be integrated in such a manner. These pave the way for a more comprehensive evaluation that takes into account more precise exposure (tissue dosimetry) and toxicity testing known as Biological Pathway Altering Dose (BPAD), linked to multiple tiers of environmental pollution.

At the prototype development stage, exposure data based on usage can be used in estimating exposure, as well as determining the chemical group of the chemical being designed. Tools such as the Advanced REACH tool (ART), INTEGRA and ConsExpo can provide integrated exposure estimates on occupational and consumer risk respectively to support the decision-making during this stage of innovation. Overall, exposure monitoring can support the SSbD toolbox by providing critical information about the levels and patterns of exposure to chemicals.

There is a plethora of frameworks that can be supported by exposure assessment tools with some of them presented below.

- Exposure levels estimation

For the exposure levels estimation can be executed calculations related to potential human and environmental exposure to chemicals and materials throughout the product lifecycle, from production to disposal. This information is incorporated for the detection of potential hazards and risks associated with human health, and guide decisions around product design and process optimization.

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- Risk Assessment

Risk assessment methodologies can assess the potential health and environmental risks associated with exposure to chemicals and materials. By providing data on toxicity, persistence, and bioaccumulation, for example, the platform can help identify hazards and inform risk management strategies. This happens in cooperation with some of other modelling tools provided by INTEGRA and the other tools that will be integrated. This could function as a basis for the extended interoperability (in line with the FAIR principles) in the complete SSbD toolbox.

- Chemical Substitution

Chemical substitution can be succeeded by estimating exposure levels and associated risks, the platform provides insights concerning material selection and product design, leading to a decision tree incorporated through the toolbox.

- Compliance with regulations

To ensure compliance with regulatory requirements related exposure to dangerous chemicals and materials a solid computational framework is needed. The platform can guide decisions around risk management and mitigation strategies, ensuring that products are designed and manufactured in compliance with relevant regulations, including SSbD framework.

Overall, providing designers with access to critical information on impacts of exposure modelling in this context. Finally, it is worth mentioning that the exposure modelling pipeline will provide the rest of the methodological pipeline with valuable pieces of information for a construction for a decision tree which will lead to the evaluation of safety and the sustainability of a material with the integration of a powerful computational tool such as INTEGRA and the other computational tools that will be integrated into the SSbD framework. The whole implementation will foster FAIRness of the computational approach promoting FAIR data and models.

4.2.1.1.3.2 PBPK modelling

A critical component in understanding exposure is data on dose at target, i.e., the dose that reaches the target for the molecular initiating event or key event in an AOP. Understanding processes of adsorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) are key for determining the fate of chemicals in biota and their hazard. ADME processes can be modelled using physiology-based pharmacokinetic or toxicokinetic (PBPK/TK) models to follow uptake and depuration processes over time. These models are based on combinations of differential equations and require detailed information on the physiology of the studied organism and chemical-specific information. Physiology data covers organ-specific information including volumes, blood flows, reproduction, growth, etc. The models are chemical specific and require information on e.g., partitioning between blood and studied tissues, and metabolism and excretion processes. Models are developed for humans and rodents but also for aquatic biota including several fish species.

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Figure 18. Multi-compartment PBPK model with 12 compartments. Excretion of the compound is from feces via gut, urine via kidney and breath via lung respectively.

Data required for model parametrization can be derived experimentally but also using computational methods including QSAR/QSPRs. Model development is currently moving towards higher resolution in number of organs, ionization processes, and new species but also towards high-throughput modelling. New techniques like read-across along with PBPK can be helpful in identifying the accumulation or disposition of new substances at early stages. The latter development is an opening for inclusion into the SSbD toolbox to inform on dose at target for emerging chemicals or yet unexplored chemicals. Specialized models like pregnancy, gestational, and lactational PBPK can predict the risk for fetus and infants helping in early prediction of disease. INTEGRA and MERLIN-Expo are tools that include PBPK models providing estimates of doses in different human tissues and supporting decision-making at this level. Additionally, integrating PBPK/TK models with exposure assessment and systems biology models can also help in developing SSbD toolbox by providing information regarding the toxicity of emerging substances.

4.2.1.1.3.3 In vitro models

In vitro models can be used to evaluate the toxicity of chemicals and to screen new chemicals for safety and efficacy. They provide mechanistic information about how a chemical may exert adverse biological effects. *In vitro* models offer the advantage of testing multiple substances and conditions at once, making them less expensive and quicker, in comparison to *in vivo* testing. They also utilize human cells, eliminating the need for extrapolation between species and they allow us to establish precise dose-response relationships, making our assessments more accurate (Fröhlich and Salar-Behzadi, 2014). Additionally, because they can describe the interaction between chemicals and living organisms on a molecular and cellular level, they are more suitable to examine and explain the mechanisms of toxicity (Romeo et al., 2020). *In vitro* findings, however, are limited in the way they relate to risk assessment since they do not directly reflect a systemic response, particularly when only one cell type is used. More intricate systems that mimic the three-dimensional structure of organs are being created to get around this restriction (Fitzgerald et al., 2015). *In vitro* studies typically involve assessing metabolic and gene expression changes following exposure to specific chemicals. Transcriptomics and metabolomics serve as valuable tools for evaluating the potential toxicity of new substances. Through these studies, we can gain early insights into potential risks associated

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with exposure. Furthermore, by analysing alterations in biological pathways, we can identify potential health hazards and enhance our understanding of the biological mechanisms underlying chemical toxicity (Cuykx et al., 2019, Ardisasmita et al., 2022).

4.2.1.1.3.4 System biology models

Systems biology models are mathematical constructs that attempt to represent the intricate relationships between various biological systems and processes. As they can offer insightful information on the potential health hazards connected to chemical exposure, these models can be a crucial element in the attempt to evaluate a risk and decide regarding its safety. These type of modelling tools will deliver insights about the hazard of using a material on cellular and molecular level returning information about potential impacts to human health. There are many pros by integrating Systems Biology models in the SSbD framework which are illustrated below.

- Predictive modelling:

Systems biology models can be used to forecast the effects of substances on the body at the tissue, cellular, and molecular levels by simulating the interactions between many biological systems and processes using mathematical equations and computational approaches. The reaction to emerging potential risks to human health and the environment can be informed by integrating this information.

- In silico testing:

In silico testing, a virtual or computer-based technique for evaluating the effects of substances without performing animal or human studies can utilize systems biology models as a tool. As a result, chemical effects can be predicted without the necessity for costly and time-consuming animal or human experiments.

- Understanding the mechanism of toxicity:

Systems biology models include details on the Molecular Initiating Events (MIE) that result in a negative consequence on human health. They behave holistically when a human is subjected to a perturbator, which is the Mode of Action (MoA) of a disruptor. Risk can be determined as a result of that exposure, and the compound's conditions of use can be assessed. Systems biology models also help to identify genetic and epigenetic alterations in a similar manner. Anomalies in the human genome, transcriptome, proteome, or metabolome as well as the regulation of these processes are among these modifications.

- Potential Biomarkers Identification:

Potential biomarkers, which are molecular indicators of exposure or effects that may be used to monitor exposure or evaluate the health impacts of substances, can be found using systems biology models. MoA will give incredibly helpful insights for categorizing substances and identifying their toxicity patterns. Several metabolic pathways, which have been identified as systems biology-based biomarkers of effect can inform on potential risks/adverse outcomes.

Dose — Response relationships:

The relationship between the dose of a chemical and the ensuing biological response can be modelled using systems biology methods. This information can be used to inform chemical distribution and provide early warning indications of a potential hazard.

- Understanding the interplay between different chemicals:

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At various stages and levels of biological processes, chemical interactions can be detected using biological models. In this process, biological processes and AI techniques are combined. As can be seen, this is a crucial feature that a cutting-edge early warning system ought to have.

- Integration with all the other tiers described.

These can be used with other models to provide a more thorough understanding of how substances like chemicals affect the human body, including exposure models, PBPK models, toxicokinetics, AI algorithms, and bioinformatics.

Moreover, in the present stage of innovation, systems biology models can support the classification of chemicals and the identification of relevant data to be supplied while a first experimental investigation can be determined. Finally, it is clear that systems biology models are a tool that may enhance decision-making by enhancing risk assessment and can be implemented into the SSbD framework. These models have the ability to handle biological perturbations on a multidimensional level, providing very valuable evidence via a variety of outputs for the techniques at the next tier of calculations while incorporating inputs from earlier layers.

4.2.1.1.3.5 NAMs

New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) are defined as any technology, methodology or approach that does not use animals and can provide information on chemical hazard and human risk assessment. (Dent et al., 2018) They can be used as alternatives to traditional animal testing and include *in silico* methods (such as QSAR and machine learning models), *in vitro* (cell cultures and organoids) and *ex vivo* (omics applications) approaches. (Thompson et al., 2021, Pamies et al., 2022, Malinowska et al., 2022, Gwinn et al., 2020) NAMs are not necessarily newly developed methods, rather, it is their application to regulatory decision making or replacement of a conventional testing requirement that is new. NAMs can mimic human biology and provide mechanistic information about how a chemical may cause toxicity in humans (Stucki et al., 2022).

Omic technologies can provide information about the molecular changes in response to chemical exposure and help identify potential toxicity pathways. Omics (transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics) can be used to identify the molecular mechanisms of toxicity and evaluate the effects of exposure to multiple substances and lead to the development of novel Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) (Miccoli et al., 2022). By combining omics with other NAMs, such as *in silico* models and high-throughput screening, a better understanding of the toxicology of the chemicals can be achieved, by linking the exposure to adverse outcomes and facilitate the creation of novel AOPs. (Sturla et al., 2014, Ram et al., 2022) Additionally, Artificially Intelligence (AI) can be one of the most crucial enablers for NAMs used in the SSbD framework, as it can process and analyze the data obtained from omics analyses and identify potential key events and biological pathways for the development of AOPs (Blümmel et al., 2023) in support of both screening and more comprehensive and mechanistically-based risk assessment. Especially in the context of SSbD, the capacity to avoid false negatives when evaluating risk on man and the ecosystem is essential. Thus, anchoring risk assessment on mechanistic understanding of the biochemical and biological processes that are induced from exposure to the compounds studied is a key methodological element that would be expected to enhance the robustness of the SSbD assessment.

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4.2.1.1.4 Testing and verification - Gate 4

Figure 19. Safety components employed in the stage-gate 4

4.2.1.1.4.1 Exposure monitoring

Exposure monitoring can support the SSbD toolbox by providing information about the levels and patterns of human and environmental exposure to chemicals. This information can be used to identify potential risks and to inform decisions about the safety and sustainability of chemicals. For example, exposure monitoring can help to identify populations or areas that are particularly vulnerable to chemical exposure, such as workers in industrial settings, residents living near contaminated sites, or children who may be more sensitive to chemical exposure. This information can be used to develop targeted strategies for reducing exposure and protecting public health. Exposure monitoring can also be used to evaluate the effectiveness of risk management strategies, such as engineering controls, personal protective equipment, or regulatory measures. This information can help to refine and improve these strategies over time, and to identify opportunities for more effective risk reduction. Furthermore, exposure monitoring can be used to evaluate the environmental impact of chemical use and to inform decisions about the safe and sustainable use of chemicals. This can help to identify areas where chemical releases are having the greatest impact and to develop strategies for minimizing these impacts. By using this information, chemists and regulators can develop and promote safer and more sustainable chemical practices that protect public health and the environment.

4.2.1.1.4.2 In vivo models

In vivo methods, as part of the broader spectrum of chemical hazard assessment, hold a significant place in ensuring the safety and sustainability of chemical substances. These methods involve the use of living organisms to assess the potential risks associated with exposure to various chemicals. While there has been a growing emphasis on alternative methods, like *in vitro* testing and computational modeling, *in vivo* studies remain indispensable. Regulatory agencies often mandate toxicity testing, including *in vivo* studies, as prerequisites for new material or product approvals (Burden et al., 2021). They provide a real-world context for evaluating chemical hazards by considering complex biological interactions, including alterations in gene expression and metabolism, and systemic effects, crucial for assessing ecosystem accumulation potential. This comprehensive approach, not only aids in understanding acute toxicity, but also long-term

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health impacts. Animal toxicological data typically establish a starting point in chemical risk assessment, determining a benchmark dosage like a no-observed-adverse-effect level (NOAEL) or its lower confidence limit and allowing the identification of suitable dosage levels for subsequent experiments. Such studies also pinpoint the organs most susceptible to damage and provide early safety indicators, like changes in organ weights or biomarker responses. Additionally, *in vivo* models can help detect biological pathways that are perturbed by chemical exposure, leading to an understanding of the mode of action of the chemicals and the determination of more effective methods to reduce their adverse effects (Kumar and Jha, 2017).

4.2.1.1.4.3 AOPs

The Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) is a structured representation of the causal or mechanistic relationships — key event relationships (KERs) - between a molecular initial event (MIE) and an adverse outcome (AO), covering multiple levels of biological organization (Ankley et al., 2010). An AOP is a sequence of events that begins with the interactions between a chemical/stressor and a biological molecule resulting in a molecular perturbation - molecular initiative event - going through a series of biological changes, known as the intermediate key events (KEs) and leading up to an adverse outcome (AO), meaningful to the safety assessment of chemicals. The adverse outcome is an apical endpoint with regulatory importance that is typically used for hazard identification and risk assessment (OECD, 2018). In the context of SSbD, AOPs can be useful tools in regulatory chemical risk assessment. In particular, AOPs can be distinguished into qualitative and quantitative AOPs. Qualitative AOPs can be used in chemical risk assessment and more specifically in hazard assessment guiding decision-making in the development of new chemicals, as they provide the knowledge concerning the series of key events (KEs), starting from the MIE and leading up to an adverse outcome (AO). Quantitative AOPs (qAOPs), on the other hand, can contribute to the risk assessment of chemicals by identifying and quantifying the amount of dose required to cause an adverse health outcome. Hence, quantitative AOPs can convert a descriptive AOP into a quantitative one, assisting in the prediction of an adverse outcome (Perkins et al., 2019).

AOPs serve as a framework that can also enhance Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessments (IATAs). When AOPs are integrated into IATA, they facilitate a more mechanistic and predictive approach to chemical risk assessment. As a result, this integration would be expected to introduce compact and reliable applications within the SSbD framework. AOP-informed IATA has the potential to guide the development of tiered testing strategies. These strategies begin with initial screening and progress to more detailed and specific testing if necessary. Such an approach optimizes resource allocation and minimizes unnecessary animal testing, resulting in quicker results. This aspect is particularly crucial for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The incorporation of AOPs into IATA fosters a more holistic and mechanistic understanding of chemical toxicity. This, in turn, enhances the accuracy of risk assessment and aligns with the principles of the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction, Refinement) in animal testing and within the SSbD framework.

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4.2.1.1.5 Production - Gate 5

Figure 20. Safety components employed in the stage-gate 5

4.2.1.1.5.1 Human biomonitoring

Human biomonitoring (HBM) entails the measurement of chemical substances or their metabolites in biological samples, such as blood, urine, teeth, or hair, to evaluate human exposure to chemicals. The application of HBM at different levels — production (occupational), use (general population), and waste (environmental) — necessitates customized approaches founded on chemical properties, exposure scenarios, safety, and sustainability concerns. The implementation of HBM studies within the SSbD framework should primarily be executed through occupational studies employing multiple methodologies. These methodologies encompass: (a) exposure assessment of workers exposed to chemicals in the production process, (b) baseline measurements of corresponding chemicals, (c) routine monitoring of workers, including individual assessments, and (d) health surveillance procedures to detect early warnings. This comprehensive framework will aid decision-makers in evaluating the safety and sustainability of a chemical.

Moreover, chemicals should also undergo testing within the general population through population surveys with random sampling. These surveys should take into account sensitive subpopulation groups that may be more vulnerable to the effects of the chemical. The key feature of these studies is their longitudinal nature, tracking changes over time within the population. Additionally, the adoption of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles within the SSbD framework will facilitate the communication of both data and metadata. This ensures that information is readily available, comprehensible, and can be effectively utilized. Last but not least, environmental HBM studies must also be incorporated into the SSbD framework, particularly in areas near disposal sites or facilities handling the chemicals of interest.

Table 9. Potential matrices, compounds, and analytical techniques for HBM studies.

Matrix	Advantages	Limitations	Compounds measured in the matrix	Techniques
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Blood, serum, plasma	There are well established standard operating procedures (SOPs) for sampling.	Invasive method (trained staff and special materials are required) Volume limitation and special conditions for transport and shipment	POPs, metals/trace elements, organic compounds, tobacco smoke. e.g.: alkylphenols, mercury, lead, BFRs, dioxins, water disinfection by-products, fluorinated compounds, organochlorine pesticides, organophosphate pesticides, phthalates, PCBs, dioxins.	Metabolomics (LC-MS, NMR), Chemical Analyses (GC-MS, ICP-MS), Gene expression analysis (Microarray, PCR)
Urine	Non-invasive method, easy to collect, no volume limitation	Composition of urine varies over time and according to the time of collection.	Metals/trace elements, organic compounds, tobacco smoke. Metabolites of environmental pollutants. e.g.: mercury, cadmium, arsenic, organochlorine compounds, BPA, organophosphate pesticides, parabens, phthalates, PAHs, benzene	Metabolomics (LC-MS), Chemical Analyses (GC-MS, ICP-MS)
Hair	Non-invasive method No special requirements for transport and storage Information about cumulative exposure during previous months.	Hair is exposed to the environment and can be contaminated. Potential variations with subject's hair colour, hair care or race may occur, and a special questionnaire is needed.	Metals/trace elements, POPs e.g.: total mercury, methylmercury, arsenic, cadmium, parabens, organochlorine compounds	Chemical Analyses (LC-MS, GC-MS, ICP-MS)
Saliva	Non-invasive, easy collection	The concentrations of analytes are lower than other matrices and as that sensitive analytical techniques are required. Furthermore, there are less publications on HBM applications.	Metals/trace elements, organic compounds, POPs, tobacco, e.g.: cadmium, phthalates, BPA, PCBs, dioxins	Metabolomics (LC-MS), Chemical Analyses (GC-MS, ICP-MS)
Placenta	Non-invasive, provides information about mother and child	Restricted to certain period of life	Metals/trace elements, POPs, organic compounds, e.g.: mercury, cadmium, lead, organochlorine pesticides, BPA, BFRs, dioxins, PCBs, PAHs, phthalates	Metabolomics (LC-MS, NMR), Chemical Analyses (GC-MS, ICP-MS)

4.2.1.2 Inputs from other PARC WPs

The contribution of the various PARC WPs to the SbD concept is graphically illustrated in Figure 21.

Figure 21. Contribution of the various WPs to the SbD concept

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4.2.1.2.1 WP2

Establishing a long-lasting, cross-disciplinary network to determine the top priorities for research and innovation in connection to chemical risk assessment is one of the larger objectives of PARC. Over time, numerous research initiatives within and outside of Europe have produced innovative methods for assessing chemical risk; however, their regulatory uptake has been constrained, primarily due to a mismatch between the requirements of the regulations and the timely incorporation of scientific findings. The main objectives of this WP are to establish and maintain a central knowledge management platform called "PARCopedia", to ensure adequate links between research activities and regulatory needs, and to create and maintain "PARCroute", a long-term strategic roadmap that ensures the sustainability of PARC results and outputs after seven years. Moreover, it will guarantee high-level conversations about the continuation of successful PARC initiatives after the seven-year period at the national and EU levels (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023). These frameworks will support with inputs PARC SSbD toolbox leading to a state — of — the — art work for stakeholders, JRC and the scientific community on global scale.

4.2.1.2.2 WP3

WP3 will help in dissemination of SSbD framework through internal and external collaborations, synergies and projects. This is something that will help SSbD toolbox to be tested and applied through a series of stakeholders and participants by evaluating all its novel aspects. The goal of PARC's communication, distribution, and exploitation strategy and plan is to connect with the various end-users of the Partnership's products effectively and intensively in order to ensure the integration of various viewpoints (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023). This work will support SSbD toolbox with various inputs that will be integrated in a framework and organized based on the inputs from this WP.

4.2.1.2.3 WP4

The work under WP4 is broken down into three tasks that aim to complete three goals: (a) continuation of the HBM4EU-established human biomonitoring platform, (b) establishment of an EU-wide environmental and multisource monitoring, and (c) continued development of cutting-edge monitoring techniques and tools (Marx-Stoelting, Rivire et al. 2023). These tasks will support PARC SSbD toolbox with multiple datasets related to human biomonitoring and environmental perspective and provide the incorporated models and case studies with the available information.

4.2.1.2.4 WP5

The work carried on in the framework of WP5 will help (a) to fill the data gaps provided by participants full filling key info in the SSbD toolbox; (b) testing strategies for the evaluation of chemicals and promotion of NAMs; (c) mechanism of toxicity identification through the use of bioinformatic algorithms and (d) adverse outcome pathways framework development and incorporation in the PARC SSbD (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023).

4.2.1.2.5 WP6

With NGRA adoption as the ultimate objective, WP6 aims to promote innovation in regulatory risk assessment by bolstering its scientific foundation. WP6 will consider both changes that can be implemented now and those that will require more research and policy creation in the future. In order to advance innovation in the regulatory risk assessment process, WP6 intends to create and implement the finest scientific advancements in risk assessment procedures. It also addresses the demands of the regulatory and policy community. WP6 will support the "one substance, one assessment" approach and help to transform the field of chemical risk assessment by developing the science of chemical risk assessment

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through a system-thinking approach, combining and connecting the best of various scientific domains, and sharing common visions and roadmaps. There are four tasks in WP6, total (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023).

PARC SSbD toolbox will perform as a final step of the safety evaluation procedure, risk assessment and sustainability in order to determine if terms of use of a compound are the proper ones. As a results of that SSbD toolbox will be able to use several computational tools that will be implemented in this WP and provide early signals to regulators and stakeholders in case that a chemical is a potential threat.

4.2.1.2.6 WP7

PARC promotes harmonization of data and exchange between different actors (scientific community, health agencies, regulators, policymakers etc.) and disciplines (exposure science, toxicology...) to promote transparency, support risk assessment, and allow for reuse. It will ensure data and associated information is FAIR and addresses the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EC, 2006) related challenges for data exchange. FAIR principles are extensively supported in Task 7.1 and Task 7.2. Data “FAIRification” is a crucial point for the implementation of SSbD toolbox due to the fact that it should be continuously fed with data (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023).

A range of advanced approaches will be developed and documented, including pooling and meta-analysis of heterogeneous datasets, uncertainty analysis, and knowledge and text mining via on-the-fly ontological mapping, Bayesian networks, machine learning and other approaches. Analytical tools will be made available as FAIR algorithms and supplied to all work packages within PARC for use and integration into toolboxes. Good practice guidelines describing the approaches and their applications for regulatory risk assessment will be published. PARC SSbD will take advantage of these algorithms in order to analyse large amounts of data, extract pieces of information from the available literature and evaluate the uncertainty of the methods used.

4.2.1.2.7 WP8

With links to the SSbD toolbox and models from other projects, this task aims to integrate the models created and the data that will be gathered and generated within PARC into a comprehensive and unified framework. It then implements this in a functional and open PARC computational tool network infrastructure. The network of PARC modelers will create a list of models and talk about the technical integration of models and tools. Significant parties, including the EFSA, ECHA, and pertinent national authorities, will be participating. In order to evaluate various methodological frameworks at each stage of the risk assessment process and to quantitatively estimate and decrease uncertainties pertinent to various risk assessment techniques, the role of uncertainty and data harmonization elements will also be taken into consideration. Compliance with FAIR principles and developing a uniform method of communication between the nodes of the PARC model network will also receive special consideration. This will improve the integrative model network architecture established by PARC's generic nature for a variety of risk assessment demands, including the use cases specified (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023).

In the framework of Task 8.2, Task 8.3 will contribute to almost all computational tiers as they are presented in the modelling tools section. The network infrastructure that will be implemented is illustrated in Figure 22 and consists of several novel modelling tools that can contribute effectively to SSbD toolbox. These tools will provide input to one another in order to evaluate safety guidelines for a compound.

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Figure 22. Models available within the PARC consortium

4.2.1.2.8 WP9

WP9, responsible for building infrastructural and human capacities aiming to bring together existing, emerging and novel concerns related to chemical hazard, exposure, and risk assessment supporting the NGRA strategies for a non-toxic environment. There are four different tasks in WP9, Task 9.1: Laboratory networking, Task 9.2 Building exposure monitoring capacities, Task 9.3: Joint activities — harmonization and Task 9.4 Training in PARC (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023). The work in the different tasks is going to help to the development of the SSbD toolbox. Laboratory networks in the different domains such as human biomonitoring, environmental monitoring, food and feed, both target and non-target analysis, toxicology and ecotoxicology, in vivo and in vitro methods will be mapped, strengthen and provide easier and consolidated the datasets for the SSbD toolbox. Important link is the link between Task 9.4 where Internal trainings in the different steps of the development of the SSbD toolbox can be hosted and give the opportunity to engage experts providing knowledge to younger researchers or stakeholders about SSbD toolbox.

4.2.2 Sustainability components

4.2.2.1 Resources and processing- and product-related aspects

The Resource and processing- and product-related aspects are a category of aspects that could impact the sustainability dimension. Hence, this category will be taken into consideration in the SSbD toolbox and the sustainability assessment. In this category, there are aspects that are relevant to and characteristic of the production process of substances, including chemicals and materials, (energy and resource efficiency, waste generation, etc.), as well as aspects of the product (durability, reparability, recycled content) affected by the resources and process decisions (feedstock type). These aspects are related to EU's aims in Ecodesign Directive (Directive 2009/125/EC) and several others such as the Energy Labelling Directive, Consumer Policy Initiative and Sustainable Products Initiative.

In more detail, as previously mentioned, material flow analysis (MFA) can be used both in the safety and sustainability assessment. Regarding the sustainability part, MFA will be a useful tool for evaluating the resource consumption (volume, characteristics and geographical location of various material flows) and to avoid unnecessary waste production of a production process by identifying and analyzing the inputs and

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outputs flows of the system. Additionally, aspects related to reducing the use of resources, their type, quantity, and efficiency are of particular importance and will be considered as part of the sustainability assessment. The use of renewable resources, the amount of water consumed and generated, the efficiency of a reaction, as well as atom economy and E-factor are some of the basic indicators for these aspects.

The aspect of circularity will be examined, promoting the use of toxic-free materials with less hazardous substances, durable, repairable, and reusable products, and more clean recycling, while minimizing the use of raw materials, waste production and carbon emissions. Furthermore, the considerations of using fully or partly recycled materials should be included. When using recycled materials, standardization of the quality would help manage chemicals in recycled materials, or at least standardization of the testing protocols for recycled materials is needed.

One other valuable aspect to be included in the SSbD toolbox is the biodegradability of a chemical, which is also a part of the safety dimension. The ability of a substance to be naturally broken down into smaller components by living organisms and absorbed into the environment without toxic releases can have positive effects on the environment by producing less waste and consuming less energy during their production. However, biodegradability of materials is not included.

Lastly, energy and in particular energy consumption and efficiency are critical components of the sustainability dimension and are going to be considered for the development and selection of more sustainable and “green” chemicals.

4.2.2.2 Environmental Dimension

The environmental dimension of sustainability is an essential component of the SSbD toolbox, and it is primarily concerned with the assessment of environmental impacts across the entire value chain. In the context of the SSbD toolbox, the environmental impact assessment will be conducted through an LCA study, modelling the chemical’s life cycle from raw material extraction to use and end of life. The assessment can be done at three levels, including the pressure, impact, and damage level. At the pressure level, there are aspects related to environmental pressures, such as water, air, and soil emissions or the use of resources. More specifically, atmospheric emissions of NO_x, SO₂, and CO₂ or the measurement of water pollution through the total organic carbon are some of the aspects considered at this level. In terms of the impact level, environmental impacts emerge from the pressures and are assessed at midpoint and endpoint levels (damage). The impacts at the midpoint level are related to categories such as climate change, human toxicity and ecotoxicity, acidification, eutrophication, etc. In more detail, the impacts of climate change will be considered by calculating the global warming potential (GWP), an indicator for the total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions per kilogram of CO₂.

The potential for ozone depletion and photochemical ozone formation, as well as the effects of particulate matter emissions, are also going to be examined in the environmental impact assessment. Additionally, one more impact category is the ionizing radiation or radioactivity of a substance, where its effects on human health will be taken into account.

At the impact level, there is also the aspect of resources (fossil, mineral, land, and water) and the impacts resulting from their consumption. This category concerns the depletion of resources (fossil and mineral) and the use of water and land. Lastly, moving on to the damage level, the emphasis will be on ecosystems and human health damage (endpoint indicators) through integrated impact assessment. To summarize, several LCIA methods (ReCipe 2016, CML, EF v3.1, USEtox, LC-IMPACT, IMPACT World+, etc.) have been

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identified that can provide characterization factors for these impact categories at the impact (midpoint) and damage level (endpoint), thereby contributing to the estimation and assessment of environmental impacts using LCA software (SimaPro, openLCA, GaBi and Umberto). Within the context of the development stages, the level of information increases moving up from early (stages 1 - 2) to later stages (stages 3 - 5). Hence, the environmental impact assessment of a chemical through the whole value chain can be performed at later stages of innovation, when there is a sufficient quantity of data regarding both the chemical itself and the overall manufacturing, distribution, use and disposal processes to conduct an LCA, progressing from a preliminary to a full assessment.

4.2.2.3 Social Dimension

The social dimension of sustainability has not been sufficiently implemented, yet it is a very crucial component of the sustainability assessment and the SSbD toolbox. As part of the sustainability assessment, the social dimension will be primarily focused on specific aspects, as identified in the JRC report on SSbD (Caldeira et al., 2022b). More specifically, the aspects that are going to be considered in the PARC SSbD toolbox are classified into the following categories: supply chain responsibility, human rights, labour rights, customer protection, and occupational health and safety. Supply chain responsibility is an approach that mainly focuses on the production of more ethical, sustainable, and socially-conscious products and materials, considering the products impacts on human health and the environment through the supply chain. This category is focused on monitoring and selecting suppliers, preventing corruption practices, and monitoring the creation of jobs. Another category of aspects that is going to be taken into account in the social sustainability assessment is customer protection. It is mainly emphasized in maintaining a code of ethics in marketing communication while measuring the impact on customers' health and safety and their basic needs.

Occupational health and safety is also a part of the social dimension, but it is also examined in the safety dimension. Hence, beyond the safety part, the monitoring of social responsibility standards, the actions for minimizing occupational exposure to noise during working activities, and the tracking of annual occupational injuries will be examined. Subsequently, the protection of human rights will be also considered, which will include the monitoring of aspects such as child labour, forced labour, the age of workers, the quality of the workers' life during their activities, the freedom of association, as well as the discriminations based on ethnicity, race, gender, etc. Finally, labour rights are also a category of the social dimension, being a combination of legal and human rights in labour conditions, such as the required number of working hours and the aspect of fair wages. In general, social sustainability assessment relies on the Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) methodology by assessing the social impacts of products and services throughout their life cycle. The consideration and choice of different stakeholder categories, as well as the assessment of positive social impacts are fundamental components of this assessment (Caldeira et al., 2022a). Social sustainability assessment will be mainly implemented during the later stages (stage 5) of the innovation process when there is adequate information about the product.

4.2.2.4 Economic Dimension

The economic dimension of SSbD encompasses both financial and non-financial aspects. Financial aspects are related to the life cycle consumption of financial resources in the implementation of SSbD principles for a chemical, material or product (R&D costs, investment and operating costs). They can be calculated along the value chains and life cycles of these substances, such as chemicals and materials, or products, using prices of goods and services that are traded on markets.

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Non-financial economic aspects of SSbD relate to the health and environmental dimensions that are generally not considered in standard economic transactions. Several economic tools are used to assign an economic value to these dimensions, through monetization techniques applied to the impacts on the environment and on human health calculated for instance with LCA tools. These non-market values of common goods (public health, healthy environments, etc.) are also referred to as “externalities”. A preliminary cost analysis can be implemented at earlier stages of innovation, but the comprehensive economic assessment will be performed at later stages (stages 4 - 5) due to the level of detail. This evaluation can be valuable for decision-making, ensuring that the available resources are used effectively throughout the whole value chain.

4.3 Socio-Economic assessment

4.3.1 Socio-Economic Analysis

Socio-Economic Analysis is a term used to cover different tools used to compare or assess the sustainability of chemicals, materials, or technologies, mainly Cost - Benefit analysis (CBA) and Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA).

4.3.1.1 Cost/Benefit Analysis

In Cost Benefit Analysis, costs of benefits are quantified in monetary terms when possible, including items for which the market does not provide a satisfactory measure of economic value (degradation, loss of functionality of ecosystems for instance, see also 5.2.2.4). In the context of SSbD, CBA calculates the social value of developing a new chemical, material compared to a baseline, and therefore the positiveness of this value and its magnitude can be used as criteria to determine if the sustainability goals of SSbD are reached for this new chemical or material.

From a technical point of view this socio-economic value is assessed in terms of the Net Present Value (NPV) of the project to develop and use the new chemical or material. The NPV is calculated by taking the difference between the present value of monetary inflows and present value of monetary outflows over a period of time.

$$NPV = n \sum_{t=1} R_t (1 + i)^t$$

Where R_t : the net benefits (inflows) — costs (outflows) during a single period t ,

i : discount rate

t : the number of time periods

As described in section 5.2.2.4, monetary values included in NPV are both financial (costs of the new chemical/material) or non-financial and represent the positive or negative values of the impact of the chemical/material on the environment. CBA relies on impact assessment tools (typically LCA) to calculate non-financial values, and on techno-economic tools (typically Life Cycle Costing, LCC) for financial values. CBA “monetizes” non-financial impacts using the environmental economics toolbox to produce monetary values that represent the socio-economic importance of sustainable development dimensions at stake (that can be health, environmental quality, j , ...).

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Several handbooks, resources, guidance exist on how to carry out and how to find and use “reference values” to monetize impacts.

4.3.1.2 Cost/Effectiveness Analysis

Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA) is a method used to determine the least cost means of achieving preset targets or goals. In the context of SSbD, CEA can be used to compare different substances (chemicals or materials), and identify most effective SSbD solutions for instance, or to compare them against sustainability benchmarks.

In the context of sustainability and SSbD, Cost effectiveness could be defined as the ratio of the cost of developing and using a new/chemical material over the improvement in sustainability (expressed in a single indicator) brought by the chemical/material over the current situation.

4.4 Multicriteria analysis (MCA)

4.4.1 General info on MCA

Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) is a multi-step process consisting of a set of methods to structure and formalise decision-making processes in a transparent and consistent manner. Over the years, MCDA has developed many methods and software to resolve the defined problems. To use the methods, it is important to define the problem, alternatives, and criteria that may be different types of costs, environmental impact indicators, social indicators, energy efficiency, quality and other specific criteria that are relevant to the problem. When there are many alternatives for one problem, it is important to find the most suitable alternative with the best cost criteria, the lowest impact on the environment, and good energy efficiency. This can be achieved by using the MCDA method as a tool for comparing alternatives. There are many methods that can be used for solving problems and they can be arranged according to different parameters. Each MCDA method has its own calculation method by which alternatives are queued and it is not possible to claim that using specific methods with the same input data will lead to the same final result. Multicriteria analysis (MCA) covers a range of appraisal techniques that have the potential to capture a wide range of impacts, which may not be readily valued in monetary terms. MCA aims to establish preferences between options by reference to an explicit set of specified objectives and associated criteria for assessing the extent to which these objectives have been achieved. Two of the key advantages of MCA are that it can allow greater stakeholder involvement and provide greater transparency to the decisions being made at all levels of appraisal. MCA includes a group of methods to co-construct and make comparisons e.g., between chemicals, materials, processes, and supply chains integrating for example environmental, economic and social impacts. There are many different methods software available under MCA.

4.4.2 Multicriteria decision making (MCDM)

Multicriteria decision making (MCDM), which is also known as multiple-criteria decision analysis (MCDA), involves computational methods that incorporate several criteria and order of preference in evaluating and selecting the best option among many alternatives based on the desired outcome. It is applied in different fields to obtain an optimum solution to a problem where there are many parameters to consider simultaneously and the decision can not be reached based on the user experiences. The application gives a ranking result based on the selected criteria, their corresponding values, and assigned weights. The effective contribution of MCDA to get a better-informed management of substances, like chemicals and

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materials, is assessed through a systematic review of the literature. After the methodological challenges involved are highlighted, the solutions of choice are selected and supported on the grounds of explicit arguments. Indicative methods to carry out MCDA include:

- Aggregated Indices Randomization Method (AIRM)
- Analytic hierarchy process (AHP)
- Analytic network process (ANP)
- Balance Beam process.
- Best worst method (BWM)
- Brown—Gibson model.

The role of hierarchical methods to address interdependent decision components, how to treat dominant decisions, how to formulate queries to a decision maker to fully represent her policy, how to improve the robustness of the analysis, and how to address both a compensatory and a non-compensatory approach to deliver both optimal and sustainable decisions, are expected to be the main methodological issues to be addressed.

For reasons of expedience, we highlight here considerations related to one of the most widely used methods for addressing complex decision-making processes such as the ones required in the case of the implementation of the SSbD framework in de novo chemicals. In practice, AHP is one of the most suitable methods for SSbD assessment, and comprises four main steps: hierarchical structuring of the problem, assignment of weights, consistency testing, and sensibility analysis:

Hierarchical structuring of the problem: The method breaks down the problem and organizes its parts hierarchically. The top level is the goal of the decision, the second level comprises the criteria, and the lowest level contains the alternatives. In the chemical process route selection problem, the goal is to select the most sustainable one.

Assignment of weights: Weights are calculated for each indicator group using the pairwise comparison given by experts and the eigenvalue method. The pairwise comparison is generally made on a ratio scale from 1 to 9, where 1 means equal importance among two indicator groups, and 9 means that one indicator group is much more important than the other.

Consistency test: To know if the weights are meaningful, that is, that there are not contradictions between the answers given by each expert during pairwise comparison, a consistency test related to the eigenvalue method is performed.

Sensibility analysis: Weights are varied in order to observe the robustness of the solution.

AHP will be implemented in the PARC SSbD toolbox among other methods for MCDA in order to provide both flexibility in terms of the methods of choice to users and stakeholders, and robustness of the results, while maintaining a high level of transparency with regard to the technical choices (e.g. weight assignment) influencing the final decision outcome.

4.5 Computational integration

4.5.1 Development of functional workflows

Computational integration aims at the development of functional workflows (model pipelines) that involve the best suited tools for the specific user request. These pipelines will be delivered automatically, in the form

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of a new “pipeline tool”, which could be a linking portal or dashboard. The automated pipeline requires that the tools have interfaces for automated running of the models. The pipelines will be tested and refined with the case studies through a continuous iterative process following a concurrent engineering approach. This is critical in order to continuously adapt the workflows on the emerging needs of the SSbD, as well as for the integration of additional tools that might become available in the course of the project. Equally important is to ensure link with databases for data that relate to various aspects of chemical safety and sustainability such as chemical structures, tonnage, phys-chem properties, toxicity, ancillary exposure data, carbon footprint and other sustainability indexes. Databases in this direction include the ECHA CLP C&L Inventory, PubChem, eChemportal, ECOTOX, RISCTOX, NORMAN, CompTox Chemicals Dashboard, CAMEO Chemicals, Chemical Entities of Biological Interest (CheBI), ChemSpider, ChemView, OpenFoodTox, ChEMBL, OSHA Occupational Chemical Database, openLCA nexus and Ecoinvent.

Another important feature of the developed workflows is that they will follow the tiered approach regarding the complexity of tools and methods, that would rely on the stage-gate innovation approach. In this sense, models of different level of complexity should be employed based on the innovation stage, as well as the availability of data. Various models that are either available within the consortium or free to access, will be interconnected through APIs. Models for safety aspects include INTEGRA, OECD SAAToolbox, ConsExpo, OECD QSAR Toolbox, QSARs lab database, VEGAHUB, GreenScreen for Safer Chemicals, AMBIT tool and ECETOC TRA. With regard to sustainability, models in the pipelines will include ProScale, EF-LCIA Method, SubSelect, USEtox and INTEGRA-LCA. Finally, FAIRification of both the models and the workflow will be done, in order to ensure broad regulatory acceptance. As a result, the PARC model network will be able to address regulatory needs through the transparent use of computational tools and FAIR data.

4.5.2 Development of user interface

A central interface that will form/describe the pipeline of the SSbD toolbox will be created. Initially, this will provide links to the individual model user interface included in the toolbox for early and late stages of innovation. Later on, user interfaces will be created for model pipelines that will be tailored for specific SSbD assessment requests.

The user interface will be web-based; in some cases (for specific tools) they may be a client-side application, executed from the web browser's window that will guide the user through the SSbD toolbox.

For authentication and authorization, we will strive for all PARC systems to have a single-sign-on (SSO). To this end, we consider Life Science Login (formerly ELIXIR AAI) as the most viable solution.

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6 APPENDIX

6.1 Additional background on SSbD considerations

Historical context

Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) is a crucial component of a comprehensive chemicals' strategy for sustainability. SSbD was introduced since at least the 1990s in fields such as civil engineering and pharmacy and prefigured by the "green chemistry" and "intrinsically safe processes", and "safe-by-design" approaches. It has been developing rapidly over the last twenty years, particularly in the field of nanomaterials and biotechnologies. It aims at reducing the risks of a chemical, a (nano)material, or more generally a product, in its design phase and therefore before it is placed on the market.

On the importance of SSbD

One of the key benefits of SSbD is that it can reduce the potential risks associated with the use of these compounds. This can be achieved through the use of safer alternatives, the combination of safety features into chemical products, the development of safer manufacturing processes, green chemistry and engineering applications and certainly, life cycle assessment principles. For instance, SSbD can be used to design chemicals that are less toxic and more biodegradable, or to develop products that are designed to reduce exposure to harmful chemicals.

SSbD is a vital approach for creating a sustainable future by designing commodities that are safer for human health, the environment and the economy as well as provide benefits such as the promotion of sustainable chemical production and use. This can be achieved by designing products that minimize the use of raw materials, are more energy efficient, are recyclable, have a lower environmental impact e.g. a lower carbon footprint. For instance, SSbD can be used to design chemicals that are made from renewable resources, or to develop products that are more easily recyclable. In addition, SSbD strategy can help to create jobs, promote economic green growth, and reduce the negative impact of chemicals on human health and the environment. One more key component that should be mentioned is that SSbD strategy promotes international cooperation on chemical safety and sustainability. This includes the development of international guidelines and regulations for the safe and sustainable use of chemicals, as well as the sharing of best practices and knowledge between countries, organizations and policy makers.

More specifically, Safe and Sustainable by Design approach in chemicals strategy is a framework that achieves sustainable development in the corresponding industry with safer processes and materials. The developing strategy includes several key elements such as (a) the promotion of green chemicals as alternatives to hazardous chemicals, (b) encouraging the use of green chemistry and engineering principles in chemical manufacturing, (c) improving the understanding of the potential risks associated with chemicals and increasing transparency in the chemical industry, (d) strengthening international cooperation on chemical safety and sustainability, (e) supporting the development and implementation of regulatory frameworks for the safe and sustainable use of chemicals, and (f) the introduction of smart computational tools in order to create data as early as possible and have a clear view of the materials. The overall goal of this strategy is to create a sustainable future for the chemicals industry, where chemicals are designed, produced, and used in a way that minimizes their negative impact on human health and the environment. This will require collaboration between governments, industry, and other stakeholders, as well as the development of new technologies and innovative solutions such as the SSbD toolbox that will be developed in the framework of Task 8.1.

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It is worth mentioning that the strategy that is developing also recognizes the crucial role that safety processes have. These processes help to identify and mitigate potential hazards, reduce the risk of accidents and injuries, and improve overall performance and efficiency. This can include everything from conducting risk assessments and testing prototypes, to implementing safety protocols and training employees on proper use and maintenance. By prioritizing safety and sustainability in the design process, organizations can not only protect the well-being of their employees and customers, but also contribute to a more sustainable future for everyone.

Green chemistry

It is obvious that green chemistry is a key ingredient in order to succeed in safety and sustainability design as well as the green engineering. The latter one concerns design, commercialization, and use of processes and products that reduce the environmental impact of the chemical industry. This includes the use of renewable and decarbonized energy sources, such as solar and wind power, to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and the use of closed-loop systems to minimize waste and conserve resources.

Artificial Intelligence

Moreover, green chemistry demands the use of advanced computational methods such as modern artificial intelligence (AI), deep learning (DL) and machine learning (ML) to predict the properties and behaviour of new chemicals before they are synthesized and produced. This can help identify potential risks early on and reduce the need for extensive testing, thus reducing the human health and environmental impact of the chemical industry.

AI is a powerful tool that can be used to improve the safety and sustainability of chemical products and processes. It has become increasingly important in the field of chemical design due to its ability to process and analyze large amounts of data, identify patterns, and make predictions. By analyzing data on the properties, toxicity, and environmental impact of various chemicals, deep learning algorithms can help identify safer and more sustainable alternatives to existing chemicals. This can be done through virtual screening techniques and prediction models for chemical properties based primarily on the structure that compounds have and unsupervised methodologies.

Links to biotechnology and Circular economy

Another innovative approach that should be mentioned concerns the use of biotechnology to produce chemicals from renewable resources such as plant-based materials. This may not only reduce the environmental impact of chemical production and human dependence on fossil fuels but also promotes the use of sustainable feedstocks.

Additionally, the SSbD strategy encourages circular economy principles, which aim to keep resources in use for as long as possible by recovering and regenerating products and materials at the end of their life which can be achieved using closed-loop systems and recycling technologies. SSbD should consider the entire life cycle ("from cradle to grave") and all the value chains involved, including recycling and reuse loops. Therefore, SSbD comes along with the Life Cycle Assessment approach, a methodology that is widely used to evaluate the environmental impact of a product or process over its entire life cycle, from raw material extraction to disposal. This helps to identify and prioritize areas for improvement and allows for the development of more sustainable products and processes. SSbD strategy also includes measures to improve the understanding of the potential risks associated with chemicals and increase transparency in the chemical industry.